

DISAC

Document Number: HORIZON-JU-SNS-2023/6G-DISAC/D4.1

Project Name:

6G for **D**istributed **I**ntelligent **S**ensing and **C**ommunication (6G-DISAC)

Deliverable D4.1

Initial specifications for protocols and orchestration solutions

The 6G-DISAC project has received funding from the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No 101139130

Deliverable D4.1

Initial specifications for protocols and orchestration solutions

Project Number:	H2020-EUK-815323HORIZON-JU-SNS-2023 - 101139130
Project Name:	<i>6G for Distributed Intelligent Sensing and Communication (6G-DISAC)</i>

Document Number:	HORIZON-JU-SNS-2023/6G-DISAC/D4.1
Document Title:	Initial specifications for protocols and orchestration solutions
Editor(s):	Kyriakos Stylianopoulos, George C. Alexandropoulos (NKUA)
Authors:	Kyriakos Stylianopoulos, George C. Alexandropoulos (NKUA), Marco Rossanese, Placido Mursia (NEC), Tan-Tho Luc, Francesca Costanzo, Benoît Denis, Emilio Calvanese Strinati (CEA), Giyyarpuram Madhusudan, Ali Al Khansa (Orange), Sami MEKKI (NOKIA), Henk Wymeersch, Hui Chen (CHAL)
Dissemination Level:	PU
Contractual Date of Delivery:	30/06/2025 (M18)
Security:	Public
Status:	Final
Version:	1
File Name:	6G-DISAC_D4.1_Final_v1.docx

Abstract

This deliverable presents the initial specifications of protocols and orchestration algorithms developed within Work Package 4 (WP4) of the 6G-DISAC project. The focus is on enabling efficient and scalable Distributed Integrated Sensing and Communication (DISAC) architectures, composed of heterogeneous and potentially semi-autonomous network devices. Novel control protocols are introduced for cooperative operations of communications, localisation, and sensing across devices with varying communication, sensing, computation, and energy capabilities. These include fully distributed and semi-distributed schemes for managing diverse node types (intelligent devices, devices with limited computational capabilities, etc.) while supporting active, passive, or hybrid roles in both sensing and communication. Additionally, orchestration algorithms that dynamically allocate sensing, computing, and communication resources across the DISAC network are introduced. To achieve objectives related to waveform design, beam control, and cooperative sensing, resource management and cooperative schemes have been developed. Emphasis is placed on supporting mobility, caching, and semantic-aware interfaces, while respecting heterogeneous hardware constraints. Together, these contributions provide a protocol-algorithm co-design framework that supports flexible deployment and robust network-level performance. The deliverable also details how these developments align with and build upon the architectural specifications from WP2 and algorithmic methods from WP3, laying a foundation for experimental integration in WP5.

Keywords

Distributed ISAC, 6G Networks, Resource Orchestration, Control Protocols, Cooperative Sensing, Distributed Computation

Disclaimer

This work has been performed in the framework of the Horizon Europe project 6G-DISAC co-funded by the EU. This information reflects the consortium's view, but the consortium is not liable for any use that may be made of any of the information contained therein. This deliverable has been submitted to the EU commission, but it has not been reviewed and it has not been accepted by the EU commission yet.

Contents

1	Introduction	12
2	Properties of DISAC Network Devices	14
2.1	Communication Aspects.....	14
2.1.1	MIMO Capabilities.....	14
2.1.2	Half- or Full-Duplex	15
2.2	Sensing Aspects	15
2.2.1	Passive and Active Antenna Elements	15
2.2.2	Passive and Active Sensing Devices.....	16
2.3	Computation and Storage Aspects.....	17
2.3.1	Reconfiguration Capabilities.....	18
2.3.2	Storage and Caching Requirements.....	19
2.3.3	Fully- or Semi-Distributed Computation.....	19
2.4	Power Consumption.....	19
3	Protocols for Distributed ISAC Architectures	20
3.1	Protocols for Heterogeneous devices.....	21
3.1.1	Contribution #P-1: Distributed Sensing Protocol for Non-Connected Targets ...	22
3.1.2	Contribution #P-2: Sensing with Connected Devices.....	25
3.1.3	Contribution #P-3: Control and Exploitation of RISs	28
3.1.4	Contribution #P-4: Reduced Beam Searching for Sensing-Aided Beamforming	30
3.1.5	Contribution #P-5: Dual-Beam RIS-Integrated Protocol.....	32
3.1.6	Contribution #P-6: Data Processing and Data representation	37
3.2	Contribution #P-7: Semantic Waveform Components in DISAC Protocols	38
3.3	Contribution #P-8: Learning-based protocols	40
4	Orchestration and Resource Allocation Algorithms for Distributed ISAC Architectures ...	43
4.1	Algorithms for Cooperative Multi-Sensor and Multi-Modal Systems.....	43
4.1.1	Contribution #O-1: Link-Level Resource Allocation for the Integration of RIS- Based Passive Objects Sensing in mmWave Communication Networks	44
4.1.2	Contribution #O-2: Cooperative Active Hypothesis Testing in the Presence of an Eavesdropper.....	48
4.1.3	Contribution #O-3: Cooperative Localisation of Active Users in Indoor Environment.....	50
4.1.4	Contribution #O-4: Opportunistic Localisation of Active Users.....	52
4.1.5	Contribution #O-5: Detecting the Presence of a Non-Cooperative RIS.....	53
4.2	Trade-offs for Dynamic Management of Computing, Communication, and Sensing Resources	54
4.2.1	Contribution #O-6: Resource Allocation for Distributed Positioning	56
4.2.2	Contribution #O-7: Resource Allocation for Trade-off Ambiguity-Accuracy.....	57
4.3	Contribution #O-8: Distributed Computation on Goal-Oriented Communications.....	59
4.4	Contribution #O-9: Distributed Autonomous Device Co-Configuration with Caching Capabilities.....	63
5	Conclusion	65
5.1	Summary of Technical Achievements	65
5.2	Cross-WP context and Outlook	66
6	References.....	66

List of Figures

Figure 1-1: Distributed ISAC architecture developed under WP2.	13
Figure 2-1: Communication technologies used in the presented works.	14
Figure 2-2: Passive and active sensing paradigms implemented through static and reconfigurable antenna designs, respectively. Reconfigurable devices may exploit the benefits from the adoption of active elements, at the cost power consumption.	16
Figure 2-3: An example of distributed computation where the controlled devices perform minimal processing before sending the data to the SePF, acting as a controller. Upon the computation of the appropriate properties (e.g., beam patterns), this information is fed back to them via control links.	17
Figure 2-4: Device with autonomous operation: Based on sensory inputs, local processing takes place on the device to determine its beam pattern. The device is endowed with sufficient computational, storage, and power capabilities.	18
Figure 3-1: Proposal for message exchange for 6G-DISAC configuration.	22
Figure 3-2: Flow-chart for optimised sensing.	25
Figure 3-3: Illustration of sensing with connected devices.	26
Figure 3-4: Message chart for sensing with connected devices.	27
Figure 3-5: RIS-aided distributed ISAC network.	28
Figure 3-6: Message exchange chart for RIS-aided distributed ISAC.	29
Figure 3-7 Non uniform channel frame and beam searching locations of the proposed framework.	30
Figure 3-8: Message exchange sequence for Rx tracking with dynamic time intervals and beam focusing locations.	32
Figure 3-9: Comparative performance of proposed dynamic frame protocol for SAC and a fixed structure approach.	33
Figure 3-10: Physical network deployment variants for distributed ISAC with dual-beam reflective RISs for the cooperative non-coherent sensing of passive targets (i.e., device-free localisation through Rx power monitoring); Examples shown with one RIS (a) or multiple RISs (b) associated with each sensing node (assuming BSs as sensing nodes SRxs).	34
Figure 3-11: Message exchange chart variants for distributed ISAC with dual-beam reflective RISs for the cooperative non-coherent sensing of passive targets (~ device-free localisation through Rx power monitoring); Example shown with a BS as main sensing node (SRx).	35
Figure 3-12: Integration of OSSDM as part of the DISAC sensing protocol.	39
Figure 3-13: Setup for autonomous configuration of ELAAs/BS, each one associated with its local DNN. Model parameters are shared among them before communication and sensing transmissions take place.	41
Figure 3-14: Time diagram for autonomous ELAA device configuration with local DNNs.	42
Figure 4-1: Example of link-level RIS-aided deployment scenario considered for the proposed resource allocation and communication-sensing trade-off study, where the UE and ambient sources (i.e., other BSs and UEs from the same dense mmWave network) play respectively the roles of SRx and STx for sensing.	45

Figure 4-2: Sequential (a, b) or concurrent (c, d) sensing and data communication services for an exhaustive (a, c) or partial/selective (b, d) “input” beam scanning of the sensing dual-beam RIS over the N possible steering angular sectors. 46

Figure 4-3: Example of average DL capacity for sequential and concurrent sensing and data communications during a service frame, as a function of the sensing spatial resolution (a) and instantaneous fluctuations of this DL capacity as a function of the service slot. 48

Figure 4-4: The proposed neural network architecture for NE-based multi-agent cooperation. Each agent passes its belief to the global feature extractor, and then, to its individual branch. The entire architecture can be evolved with typical NE algorithms, such as CoSyNE. 49

Figure 4-5: Average episode stopping time of single-agent hypothesis testing for different values of the threshold for eavesdropper’s posterior detection error probability E. 50

Figure 4-6: Deployment scenario for indoor user localisation with mobile D-MIMO-AGVs and fixed beacons. 51

Figure 4-7: CDF of the IoT device localisation error for different beacon deployments. 52

Figure 4-8: Illustration of opportunistic ISAC scenario with RIS. 53

Figure 4-9: Performance of the proposed rogue RIS detection strategy (dSVDD-scan B) and baselines in terms of average delay needed for detection over the number of subcarriers. ... 54

Figure 4-10: Distributed positioning scenario where resource allocation is applied to BS and RIS selection as well as transmission power toward simultaneous localisation of multiple UEs.... 56

Figure 4-11: Deployment of a distributed ISAC system exploiting communication functionality and sensing ambiguity..... 58

Figure 4-12: Trade-offs between capacity and accuracy in OFDM ISAC Systems under different PSL constraints. 59

Figure 4-13: (a) Accuracy Optimisation (b) PSL Optimisation 59

Figure 4-14: Illustration of proposed deployment strategy for goal-oriented computation over-the-air integrating stacked metasurfaces as hidden neural network layers. 60

Figure 4-15: Block diagram and computation flow for the proposed end-to-end goal-oriented framework where the metasurface-parametrizable channel acts as an intermediate DNN component. Both the cases of reconfigurable and static metasurfaces are included, entailing different procedures during the forward and backward passes. Notation explanation and details are given in [SDA25]. 61

Figure 4-17: Performance of metasurfaces-integrated neural networks compared to no-metasurface and traditional communications baseline over decreasing transmission power levels as training time evolves..... 62

Figure 4-16: Performance of different variations of goal-oriented neural networks with integrated over-the-air metasurfaces as computational layers on a classification setup without CSI knowledge at the CSI. 62

Figure 4-18: Architecture of proposed DNN for antenna configuration of ELAA/RIS devices based on local CSI. 64

Figure 4-19: Numerical evaluation of the proposed NE-MBACNN approach for cooperative training of DNN controllers for ELAAs..... 65

List of Tables

Table 3-1: Mapping of 6G-DISAC contributions to their corresponding protocols.	20
Table 3-2: Characteristics of protocol contributions for ISAC on heterogeneous devices.	21
Table 3-3: Device specifications of Contribution #P-1.....	23
Table 3-4: Device specifications of Contribution #P-2.....	26
Table 3-5: Device specifications of Contribution #P-3.....	28
Table 3-6: Device specifications of Contribution #P-4.....	30
Table 3-7: Device specifications of Contribution #P-5.....	35
Table 3-8: Device specifications of Contribution #P-8.....	41
Table 4-1: Physical and signal properties of contributions related to cooperative and multi-sensor orchestration DISAC algorithms.....	43
Table 4-2: Physical and signal properties of contributions of Sections 4.2, 4.3, and 4.4.	55

List of Acronyms

AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AoA	Angle of Arrival
AoD	Angle of Departure
AP	Access Point
BF	Beamformer
BS	Base Station
CDF	Cumulative probability Density Function
CoSyNE	Cooperative Synapse Neuro-Evolution
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CRB	Cramér–Rao Bound
CSePF	Centralised Sensing Processing Function
CSI	Channel State Information
D-MIMO	Distributed MIMO
DISAC	Distributed Intelligent Sensing and Communication
DL	Downlink
DMA	Dynamic Metasurface Antenna
DNN	Deep Neural Network
ELAA	Extremely Large Antenna Array
FFN	Feed Forward Neural Network
FoV	Field of View
GNN	Graph Neural Network
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite Systems
GO	Goal-Oriented
HRIS	Hybrid Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface
IoT	Internet of Things
ISAC	Integrated Sensing and Communication
KG	Knowledge Graph
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LLM	Large Language Model
LoS	Line-of-sight
LSePF	Local Sensing Processing Function
Ma-MIMO	Massive Multiple-Input Multiple-Output
MC	Monte Carlo
MIMO	Multiple-Input Multiple-Output

MISO	Multiple-Input Single-Output
ML	Machine Learning
MLW	Main Lobe Width
MSE	Mean Squared Error
NE	Neuro-Evolution
NLoS	Non-Line-of-Sight
OAC	Over-the-Air Computation
OFDM	Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing
OSSDM	Orthogonal Semantic Sequency Division Multiplexing
PPP	Poisson Point Processes
PRU	Positioning Reference Unit
PSL	Peak Side-lobe Level
QoS	Quality of Service
RF	Radio Frequency
RFC	Radio Frequency Chains
RFID	Radio Frequency IDentifier
RIS	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface
RIS-C	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface-Controller
RTT	Round-Trip-Rime
RU	Remote Unit
Rx	Receiver
SAC	Sensing-Aided Communications
SemCom	Semantic Communications
SeMF	Sensing Management Function
SePF	Sensing Processing Function
SIM	Stacked Intelligent Metasurface
SINR	Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio
SNR	Signal-to-Noise Ratio
SRx	Sensing Receiver
SSA	Sensing Service Area
SSE	Semantic Spectral Efficiency
ST	Sensing Target
STx	Sensing Transmitter
SVD	Singular Value Decomposition
TDMA	Time-Division Multiple Access
TDoA	Time-Difference-of-Arrival

TTI	Transmission Time Interval
Tx	Transmitter
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UE	User Equipment
UL	Uplink
WF	Water-Filling
WP	Work Package
WT	Walsh Transform

1 Introduction

Integrated Sensing and Communications (ISAC) is posed as one of the fundamental pillars of 6G [LLL+24]. The joint utilisation of network resources for the undertaking of both applications has the potential to offer substantial performance benefits with minimal to low increases in design, deployment, and operational costs. Even more so, the use and cooperation of distributed network devices is essential in orchestrating such networks. By providing channel and signal diversity, sharing of collected data and underlying processing, as well as complementary modes of operation, distributed devices may be cooperatively organised to provide network-level objectives that are difficult or impossible to achieve with centralised architectures [CAG24]. The design of each device for particular functionalities (e.g., beam focusing to predefined spots, passive listening, or tuneable reflections), simplifies hardware and power constraints, reducing the requirements of the overall architecture [GMB+25]. For Distributed ISAC (DISAC) architectures to fully realise their potential, however, open challenges remain to be solved. Particularly, the interconnection and interoperation of multiple, potentially semi-autonomous, and heterogeneous devices requires dedicated and advanced protocols. At the same time, more elaborate orchestration and resource allocation algorithms need to be implemented. The timely and accurate use of network resources regarding communication, sensing and computation operations is instrumental in achieving the system objectives while achieving desired efficiency.

The 6G-DISAC Project addresses the above challenges by providing a novel design for 6G systems of distributed devices that jointly perform communication, sensing, and localisation. Especially, the focus of Work Package (WP) 4 lies in developing novel scalable and flexible resource allocation and distributed computation frameworks enabling efficient ISAC that balance resources between communications and sensing, while adapting to environments with different numbers of connected nodes, as well as to mutating system functionalities and objectives. This deliverable presents the initial specifications for contributions developed under the first two of its tasks:

- The goal of Task 4.1 is to develop novel protocols (i.e., control schemes and signalling) that enable effective ISAC operations in wireless networks with heterogeneous devices, in terms of communications, sensing, computation, and storage capabilities as well as power consumption. In contrast to conventional centralised approaches, this task considers fully distributed schemes for actuation and decision making, as well as semi-distributed schemes where sensed data is collected in distributed fusion centres. Energy-autonomous, energy-supplied or energy-neutral devices are considered, alongside of multi-antenna devices with active, passive or hybrid elements, while intelligent or of very basic sensing capability network nodes play the role of interacting agents.
- Task 4.2 deals with the orchestration of DISAC's cooperative multi-sensor architectures, and, in particular, with the design of efficient algorithms to dynamically assign computing, communication, and sensing resources to different types of network nodes, while meeting different resource and device-hardware constraints. Exploiting relevant protocols from Task 4.1, distributed sensing and communication schemes, supporting low-latency, edge caching and computation, mobility management of active users and passive targets, as well as conventional and semantic interfaces are designed. Efficient distributed optimisation algorithms for sensing and communications are devised, aiming to jointly optimise multi-antenna transmissions and receptions, as well as the reflective beamforming of multi-functional RISs for both localisation, sensing, and sensing-aided communications, under heterogeneous energy-budget and computation constraints among the different types of involved nodes.

To achieve the WP-level objectives, WP4 maintains close interactions with the rest of the WPs. In the context of this deliverable, the contributions presented have a strong relationship with the architecture presented under WP2 [6GDISAC-D22]. The developed protocols enhance the functionality of the architectural components (shown in Figure 1-1). The Key Performance Indicators

Figure 1-1: Distributed ISAC architecture developed under WP2.

(KPIs) and relevant metrics presented in [6GDISAC-D21] are addressed by the algorithmic approaches. The interoperation of protocols and algorithms offer the orchestration and high-level decision making in the use cases presented under WP2 as well as an orchestration point of view for the experimental demonstrations of WP5. Finally, the technical advancements of this deliverable have been developed largely in parallel with WP3, which focuses on algorithmic methods for joint communication and sensing at physical layer level. In that regard, waveforms, algorithms, and technological enablers presented in [6GDISAC-D31] are leveraged to design relevant protocols and orchestration methodologies. In particular, each algorithmic contribution of [6GDISAC-D31] is accompanied by a corresponding operational protocol. As will be mentioned in the presentation of WP3/WP4 contributions, multiple such contributions may correspond to the same D4.1 protocol, since they are presented at a high abstraction level to admit possible variations, while particular WP3 contributions necessitate their individual messaging exchange aspects. Regardless, the protocols and algorithmic contributions of this deliverable are more general than the specific approaches of WP3, to the purpose of being integrated to the overall DISAC architecture, without the need for exact knowledge of the communication and sensing operation.

The remainder of this deliverable is organised as follows: Section 2 discusses the properties of DISAC devices offering an overview of their heterogeneous aspects and requirements. Section 3 contains the initial specifications for contributions related to DISAC protocols for communications, sensing, and localisation, addressing heterogeneous devices, semantic and ISAC waveforms, as well as learning and semi-autonomous devices. Initial specifications for distributed algorithmic contributions are given in Section 4, detailing orchestration approaches for multi-sensor and multi-modal architectures, resource allocation schemes exploiting trade-offs between performance and requirements, as well as orchestration methods for distributed computation and autonomous agents. Finally, Section 5 provides a brief summary of the technical achievements, as well as perspectives related to future work.

2 Properties of DISAC Network Devices

The goal of this section is to highlight the different levels of heterogeneous devices considered in 6G-DISAC in order to provide a common overview, nomenclature, and motivate the proposed protocol and orchestration contributions. As described in [RISE-D26], the envisioned DISAC network architecture accommodates heterogeneous devices with different capabilities and requirements, thereby enhancing the network’s ability to collect and process data in a distributed way. Therefore, four key aspects are identified to be considered when designing distributed network protocols and

orchestration algorithms, which are described in detail in the following. Specifically, (i) communication aspects, which include hardware considerations such as the number of antennas, half- or full-duplex operations; (ii) sensing aspects, including whether the device is passive, active or hybrid; (iii) computation aspects, which refer to the computing power of the device, and lastly; (iv) power budget considerations.

2.1 Communication Aspects

Different capabilities and technologies are considered (Figure 2-1), such as Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) variations, including Massive MIMO (Ma-MIMO), Distributed MIMO (D-MIMO) and Extremely Large Antenna Arrays (ELAA), hybrid/analog beamforming, and Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RISs), as well as half- or full-duplex.

2.1.1 MIMO Capabilities

The envisioned DISAC architecture supports single and multi-antenna devices, since the latter enable highly precise beamforming, which is exploited for maximising both the communication rate and sensing accuracy, as well as the use of novel ISAC waveforms [SCE23]. Such heterogeneous capabilities need to be considered when designing orchestration algorithms for distributed and cooperative communication and sensing, as presented in Section 4. Different types of MIMO devices are considered, including Ma-MIMO [SSK+18], i.e., devices equipped with a large number of antenna elements, which provide numerous spatial degrees of freedom enabling multi-user operations, as well as D-MIMO [MBD+14], i.e., distributed Remote Units (RUs) (antennas) over the network, as is the case of cell-free systems. Additionally, ELAA [WZD+24], i.e., devices with a large number of semi-active or passive beamforming capabilities,

Figure 2-1: Communication technologies used in the presented works.

and RISs [LLM+21], both of which enable precise and advanced beam control and spatial resolution, are envisioned as key elements of the DISAC architecture. While the concept of ELAA

is similar to Ma-MIMO, they differ in scale, deployment, and application. Indeed, Ma-MIMO uses dozens to hundreds of co-located antennas at a BS to serve multiple UEs and boost spectral efficiency, typically in 5G networks. ELAA, by contrast, distributes a much larger number of antennas over a wide physical area, enabling ultra-high spatial resolution and reliability, and is seen as a key concept for future 6G and smart environments. In particular, such aforementioned devices may come with different levels of automation, including non-reconfigurable, reconfigurable after control, and autonomously reconfigurable devices. In all such cases, the challenge in the design of network protocols for distributed ISAC (See Section 3) consists in enabling the coexistence of all such devices under a unified framework.

2.1.2 Half- or Full-Duplex

The design of both network protocols (Section 3) and orchestration algorithms (Section 4) must also consider devices operating in both half- or full-duplex. Indeed, in the former case, the transmission and the reception of signals happen in separate resources, while in the latter case, both happen simultaneously. As described in WP3 of this Project, monostatic radars operate in full-duplex mode and do not require synchronisation methods since the receiver and the Transmitter (Tx) are co-located, while bistatic and/or multistatic sensing is implemented in half-duplex mode and requires synchronisation between transmitters and receivers. In this regard, in Section 3 of this document, a distributed sensing protocol is outlined, which is applicable to both half- and full-duplex operations.

2.2 Sensing Aspects

Sensing technologies are discussed in terms of power in the reception elements (active, passive, or hybrid sensory elements) and in terms of their effect on the radio environment (active or passive sensing). Deliverable D3.1 [6GDISAC-D31] focuses on developing sensing algorithms and systems in terms of DISAC. Deliverable D2.2 [6GDISAC-D22] and its future updated version under D2.4 further include comprehensive taxonomies in terms of heterogeneous sensing devices and their implications on the overall architecture. Conversely, this section presents a brief overview of the individual characteristics of potential sensing devices to highlight the need for dedicated protocols and orchestration schemes that will be presented next.

2.2.1 Passive and Active Antenna Elements

One of the prime considerations for antenna devices within the DISAC architecture is the use of passive or active reception elements. This taxonomy refers to MIMO devices such as ELAAs and RISs in terms of their beamforming requirements and capabilities.

Passive elements have the benefits of only minimal power consumption and can thus be easily attached to distributed physical devices that constitute part of a cooperative network. As such, they are suitable for large D-MIMO implementations of Sensing Receivers (SRxs) of multistatic sensing to achieve channel and signal diversity from the perspective of different fields of view. While they do not include active reception components, i.e., Radio Frequency Chains (RFCs) for signal capturing, conversion, and baseband processing, they can be used as parts of extended SRx nodes by performing operations such as signal reflection, refraction, focusing (lens), therefore reducing the requirements for deployed expensive RFCs.

On the contrary, active elements have power amplifiers, partial, or even full RFCs incorporated within their cell design. This enables the corresponding MIMO devices not only to implement more advanced beam design policies, but also to perform baseband processing in the RU. Base Stations (BSs) and User Equipment (EU) devices evidently fall under this category. Interestingly, recent advances in RIS technology [AAS+21] have proposed hybrid unit cell designs that can either (passively) reflect the incident signal or operate in active mode for reception. In practice, only a small portion of active elements is needed [AVW22], which offers scalability, as needed by ELAA and Ma-MIMO implementations. Such designs may either act as additional SRxs

providing extra fields of view [HFV+23] or utilise their individual measurements for autonomous/semi-autonomous configuration [ADS+22]. In the context of this deliverable, this family of devices will be referred to as Hybrid RISs (HRISs), with the exact capabilities the individual devices being specified per case. While passive antenna designs can be configured similar to existing RUs by a central Sensing Processing Function (SePF), hybrid and active devices necessitate the development of novel protocols and resource allocation schemes that balance power consumption, local data exchange and associated benefits, since such devices may have multiple functional roles.

2.2.2 Passive and Active Sensing Devices

The operational mode and hardware capabilities of sensing devices play a critical role in shaping the design of sensing algorithms (see also [6GDISAC-D31]). These, in turn, have a direct impact on the required communication protocols and orchestration schemes within distributed ISAC systems.

Passive sensing refers to devices that solely collect incident electromagnetic signals without altering the nature of those signals prior to reception. These devices typically consist of antennas and RFCs that capture ambient or externally generated signals for local or centralised processing. Crucially, passive sensors do not exert any influence on the signal's spatial, temporal, or spectral characteristics before reception. Examples include:

- Basic Receiver (Rx)-only antenna nodes without beamforming capabilities,
- Internet of Things (IoT) devices performing signal strength measurements from surrounding transmitters,
- Radio telescopes or spectrum monitoring receivers in surveillance applications.

In contrast, active sensing devices interact with the wireless environment in ways that can alter or shape their own measurements, typically as a response to a feedback signal. This interaction can be at the signal level (e.g., emitting probing signals) or at the hardware level (e.g., reconfiguring antenna properties). Active sensors often include capabilities such as:

- Beamforming or antenna steering, as in MIMO or ELAA, which dynamically adjust the reception directionality to improve spatial resolution,

Figure 2-2: Passive and active sensing paradigms implemented through static and reconfigurable antenna designs, respectively. Reconfigurable devices may exploit the benefits from the adoption of active elements, at the cost power consumption.

Figure 2-3: An example of distributed computation where the controlled devices perform minimal processing before sending the data to the SePF, acting as a controller. Upon the computation of the appropriate properties (e.g., beam patterns), this information is fed back to them via control links.

- Frequency agility, where receivers adapt their listening bands to target specific signal characteristics,
- Reactive reconfigurable hardware, such as intelligent surfaces with embedded sensing logic that modify reflection patterns based on feedback or observed signals.

A form of active sensing through reconfiguration may also be achieved through alternation on the device’s properties through pre-defined schemes (e.g., beam sweeping and scanning for reconfigurable antennas or combing patterns in spectrum sensing equipment), ignoring feedback signals. In such cases, one needs basic control signalling. The distinction between passive and active sensing, as illustrated in Figure 2-2 is particularly relevant in DISAC deployments, where nodes may vary significantly in their ability to contribute to joint communication and sensing tasks. While passive nodes provide sufficient coverage with low power and complexity overheads, active nodes offer adaptable and intelligent measurement capabilities at the cost of increased complexity and coordination requirements. Investigating this dichotomy is essential for designing efficient orchestration strategies that optimally allocate tasks, manage interference, and leverage the sensing capabilities of heterogeneous nodes.

2.3 Computation and Storage Aspects

Three levels of computation capabilities are defined that according to their respective control requirements. Namely, (i) passive devices that do not perform computation and require no configuration; (ii) devices that perform basic local computation and can be reconfigured upon the reception of control signals (e.g., Figure 2-3); and (iii) devices with sufficient computational power than can autonomously process their received signals and re-configure themselves (e.g., Figure 2-4). Additionally, the capabilities in terms of storage and local caching of signals are considered to highlight the different options of fully distributed computing nodes and the semi-distributed computation offered by fusion centres.

Figure 2-4: Device with autonomous operation: Based on sensory inputs, local processing takes place on the device to determine its beam pattern. The device is endowed with sufficient computational, storage, and power capabilities.

2.3.1 Reconfiguration Capabilities

Leveraging the taxonomy presented in Section 2.3.3 of [6GDISAC-D22], a discussion on the different types of devices and their associated requirements for protocol and orchestration design is given below. In effect, sensing and communication nodes in DISAC systems exhibit varying levels of reconfigurability:

- Non-reconfigurable devices, such as static RISs, passive reflectors, and Radio Frequency Identifier (RFID) tags, have fixed configurations determined at deployment. These devices require no control-plane interaction, making them ideal for low-cost, low-power deployments. Protocols must simply account for their static behaviour in overall coordination without expecting reconfiguration. Nevertheless, orchestration algorithms may exhibit various levels of sophistication, e.g., by determining which passive device is to be activated by performing beamforming toward it [RYI+24].
- Remotely reconfigurable devices (e.g., BSs, relays, standard RISs) allow for dynamic updates to their internal state via a central or distributed controller (similar to the active sensing methodology illustrated in Figure 2-2). These devices require dedicated control channels and protocols that ensure timely, synchronised reconfiguration in response to network objectives or environmental changes. As highlighted in [6GDISAC-D22], their operation is equivalent to that of RU in the O-RAN architecture [PBD+23]. The operation and resource allocation of distributed reconfigurable devices embedded on networks with Centralised SePF (CSePF) and Sensing Management Function (SeMF) entities is especially considered in Sections 3 and 4 of this Deliverable.
- Autonomously reconfigurable nodes can sense and adapt locally using embedded intelligence. Examples include RISs with on-board sensing and processing, such as those discussed in the previous section. Protocols for these devices must support decentralised decision-making, while also enabling lightweight synchronisation or intent exchange with the rest of the network when needed. Resource allocation algorithms capitalise on

the abilities of such devices, offering trade-offs between local processing and data exchange.

2.3.2 Storage and Caching Requirements

Since the DISAC architecture presented in [6GDISAC-D22] contains various distributed devices, the storage and caching capabilities of each node vary significantly depending on their role, compute availability, and reconfigurability. This heterogeneity must be explicitly considered in orchestration protocols. Devices with active sensing functions or dynamic control states may require local storage for received signal traces, partial inference outputs, or policy updates, enabling quick local reactions or control decisions without frequent backhaul interactions.

In contrast, passive or non-reconfigurable devices may operate with minimal or no local storage, simply forwarding raw measurements or reacting statically. Protocols must therefore be designed to allocate memory-intensive operations to capable nodes, offload unnecessary buffering from constrained devices, and ensure that the overall caching strategy aligns with latency, bandwidth, and energy efficiency goals. This coordination is especially important for distributed learning and sensing tasks, where timely access to recent or context-specific data directly impacts performance.

2.3.3 Fully- or Semi-Distributed Computation

The available compute resources across the network can range from high-performance edge nodes to ultra-lightweight passive elements. This uneven distribution of computational power necessitates orchestration schemes that explicitly distinguish between fully- and semi-distributed processing models. In a fully distributed setting, devices may locally process sensed data, perform inference, or even optimise their own control decisions with minimal external coordination. Architecturally, such entities may be viewed as local SePFs alongside their ISAC role. This category refers to standard RU devices, as well as devices with onboard reconfiguration, sensing, and/or storage capability. In fact, the necessity for local processing is closely linked to the support of such features by the device's hardware. This capability for distributed computation paves the way for co-operation by semi-autonomous agents and is further examined by the contributed algorithms and protocols.

Semi-distributed approaches, on the other hand, delegate part of the computation to more capable nodes, like CSePFs collocated with other edge entities, such as BSs. These strategies are particularly relevant when local compute is insufficient or when synchronisation across nodes is required. Protocols must therefore be flexible, supporting both autonomous device behaviour and coordinated computation paths, while minimising communication overhead and ensuring real-time responsiveness across the DISAC network. Pertinent data representation approaches and semantic interfaces developed in the context of 6G-DISAC present possible choices for the transmission of intermediate representations that balance trade-offs between computing and communication resources.

Finally, Over-the-Air Computation (OAC) strategies can be highlighted as being particularly useful in DISAC scenarios: part of the computation takes place by the effects of the wireless propagation medium. The superimposition of wireless signals, the reconfiguration of the channel, as well as tunable metasurfaces offer means, under which, information may not only be transmitted, but also processed while travelling to the Rx [SDA25]. As a result, preliminary investigations on OAC approaches for semantic and goal-oriented communications have been included in this deliverable.

2.4 Power Consumption

Power availability fundamentally shapes the sensing, actuation, and processing roles that DISAC devices can perform. For the foreseen architecture to include both energy-autonomous nodes, such as battery-powered Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), and energy-supplied ones

like RUs or edge-hosted SePFs, corresponding resource allocation schemes must be implemented that particularly address the requirements of each device. Additionally, the orchestration protocols should promote sparse communication and data exchange when power-constrained devices are considered for energy conservation.

In particular, it is difficult for devices operating under tight power budgets to support continuous active functionalities. For instance, energy-harvesting sensors may only intermittently activate their receivers or offload processing entirely. Protocols involving such nodes must limit communication and reconfiguration demands while enabling opportunistic participation through light-weight signalling and sparse data exchange.

In contrast, devices with stable power that is provided through the core infrastructure can sustain active sensing, local computation, and coordination. These nodes play a critical role in maintaining DISAC functionality by assisting lower-power agents and supporting distributed ISAC workloads. As such, protocol design must explicitly accommodate the energy profile of each device, optimising network behaviour through power-aware orchestration and adaptive role assignment. Energy efficiency is still an important KPI under such instances, as well, with the proposed resource allocations schemes adhering to power budget requirements, or devising novel data compression (e.g., semantic) and computation (e.g., OAC) oriented ISAC frameworks.

3 Protocols for Distributed ISAC Architectures

This section considers the protocol aspects of DISAC. It addresses the different features and characteristics of devices discussed in the previous section, as well as the architectural elements of WP2. Different contributions are presented, considering sensing of passive targets, localisation of active users, passive localisation of active distributed RISs, data exchange and Sensing Aided Communications (SAC), ISAC and semantic waveforms, as well as protocols for federated learning. Each protocol is accompanied by its respective physical deployment scenario figure that depicts the considered devices and communication/sensing/control links, as well as its time sequence diagram, illustrating the main events and data exchanges taking place during operation. Nevertheless, the protocols have been described at a high abstraction level to accommodate multiple variations and instantiations corresponding to concrete algorithms from WP3 [6GDISAC-D31] or resource allocation and orchestration schemes from Section 4. In fact, all such contributions are linked to their respective protocol – either falling under variations of some of the proposed general-purpose protocol of Section 3.1, or by defining purposely-developed protocol generation, as illustrated in Table 3-1, in which contributions starting with #A-, #B-, and #C- correspond to contributions from [6GDISAC-D31], while contributions numbered as #P- and #O- are presented in the current document.

Table 3-1: Mapping of 6G-DISAC contributions to their corresponding protocols.

Protocol	Main scenario	Contributions from D3.1 that make use of it
#P-1	Sensing of non-connected targets	#A-4, #B-10, #B-11, #B-12, #B-13, #B-14, #B-15, #C-2, #O-5
#P-2	Sensing of connected targets	#A-3, #A-5, #B-3, #B-4, #B-7, #B-8, #B-9, #O-8
#P-3	Orchestration of RIS devices	#A-2, #B-1, #B-2, #B-6, #O-2, #O-3, #O-4, #O-1, #O-6
#P-4	Dynamic beam searching	#B-5, #C-3

#P-5	RIS-empowered sensing	#B-10, #O-1
#P-6	Exchange of data representations	#C-1
#P-7	Sensing via semantic waveforms	#A-1
#P-8	Federated learning of sensing devices	#O-9

3.1 Protocols for Heterogeneous devices

In distributed ISAC architectures, network protocols play a pivotal role in ensuring seamless coordination between sensing and communication tasks. These architectures rely on a diverse range of devices, such as the ones outlined in Section 2, operating across different frequency bands, communication standards, and computational/energy/storage capabilities. The challenge lies in designing network protocols that can support low-latency, high-reliability data exchange while accommodating the heterogeneous nature of the system components. Moreover, these protocols must support strict synchronisation, real-time data sharing, and dynamic resource allocation, ensuring efficient sensing, decision-making, and actuation across distributed nodes. This section outlines novel distributed ISAC protocols developed within the Project, focusing on their scalability, interoperability, and ability to support heterogeneous devices, while a brief overview of the proposed contributions is given in Table 3-2.

Table 3-2: Characteristics of protocol contributions for ISAC on heterogeneous devices.

	Contr. #P-1	Contr. #P-2	Contr. #P-3	Contr. #P-4	Contr. #P-5	Contr. #P-6
Protocol Objective or Scenario	Sensing of non-connected targets	Sensing with connected devices	General RIS-aided network for ISAC	Dynamic frame duration and beam searching	Sensing of passive targets through RISs	Data representation in distributed processing
Key-enabler	Distributed STxs/SRxs with centralised SeMF	Distributed STxs/SRxs communicating with UE	Multiple RISs	Hybrid beamforming	RIS with dual beam construction capabilities	Local processing and fusion centres
Key benefit(s)	Exploit pilot for target angle, range and Doppler estimation through device selection.	Exploit UE-reported measurements as extra sensing information.	Support and orchestration of multiple for RISs	Reduced number of pilots and the number of searching beams required for user tracking	Reduced hardware requirements at STx/SRx	Flexibility of processing options
Implementation cost	Distributed processing units	Use of UE resources	Additional control channels	Continuous QoS reporting by the UE, large antennas	RIS deployment	Potential complexity
Indoor/outdoor	Both	Both	Both	Outdoor	Both	Both
LoS/NIoS conditions	Both	LoS between UE and target	Both (LoS between UE and RISs)	LoS	Both (LoS between UE and RIS)	
Uplink/Downlink/Full-Duplex	All	Downlink	All	Downlink	UL/DL	All

Frequency	Agnostic	Agnostic	Agnostic	FR2	FR2 / mmWave at 28GHz	Agnostic
Bandwidth	Wideband mostly	device-specified BW	Agnostic - Narrowband	Narrow-band	Agnostic - Narrowband	High bandwidth
Near-field/Far-field regime	Both	Both	Both	Near-field	Both	N/A
Time synchronisation requirements	Tight (between STx/SRx)	Tight (between STx/SRx)	Tight or minimal for autonomous RIS	Moderate (near-real time)	Loose synchronisation	Tight

3.1.1 Contribution #P-1: Distributed Sensing Protocol for Non-Connected Targets

Motivations and Challenges

Classical message exchange schemes for target sensing often fall short in providing accurate and reliable results, primarily due to their reliance on centralised processing and limited adaptability to complex environments. These traditional protocols struggle to efficiently handle noise, interference, and the dynamic nature of real-world scenarios, leading to suboptimal sensing performance. In centralised sensing setups, dealing with noisy measurements often require increased message exchange between sensors and processor unit, especially in rapid changing environment, which can introduce communication overhead, latency and ultimately degrade the perception accuracy of the sensed data. To overcome these limitations, a new messaging ex

Figure 3-1: Proposal for message exchange for 6G-DISAC configuration.

change scheme based on distributed transmitters and receivers has emerged as a necessity. By leveraging distributed processing, this approach enables enhanced collaboration, parallel

data handling, and redundancy across the network, significantly improving the robustness and accuracy of target sensing. The distributed nature of the system ensures adaptability, scalability, and reduced latency, making it better suited for modern sensing applications in dynamic and resource-constrained environments.

Deployment Scenario

The new proposed message exchange scheme aims to significantly enhance sensing performance. The approach depicted in Figure 3-1 illustrates a distributed sensing protocol based on multiple transmitters and multiple receivers. This signalling exchange, which aligns with the architecture shown in Figure 1-1, not only facilitates more effective target detection and tracking but also introduces the concept of distributed local processing functions. These Local SePF (LSePF) collaborate to optimise the system's overall performance while minimising communication delays. By distributing the computational workload across multiple nodes, the system achieves higher efficiency, reduced latency, and improved reliability, making it a robust solution for next-generation sensing applications.

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

Several SRx and Sensing Transmitter (STx) units can be deployed in a distributed configuration across the designated space, for enhanced sensing performance, as illustrated in in Figure 3-1. The sensing client initiates a sensing request to the SeMF that selects the appropriate devices in the sensing service area. The selected devices, particularly UEs, may refuse the request due to constraints such as energy usage or computational overhead. Once the device selection is completed, the SeMF runs the configuration, orchestration and resource allocation schemes needed to fulfil the sensing service. The selected STxs then send beacon signals that are reflected and refracted by the ST, and are then collected by the SRxs. A first-level processing takes place at the LSePF of each SRx that provides easy access and offers a varying level of processing power depending on the device’s specifications, as discussed in Section 2. Leveraging appropriate data representations, the processed sensing signal is transferred to the CSePF for data fusion and final processing, while the final result is forwarded to the client through the SeMF.

By being strategically placed, coverage and redundancy are increased, and data accuracy is improved. Combining sensing signals from several SRxs leads to important fusion gains: Occlusions are better managed, resolution is optimised, and the monitored environment can be comprehensively analysed. Furthermore, fault tolerance is improved, as the impact of a single unit's failure on the overall sensing capabilities is minimised. Additionally, the LSePF could also be distributed across the network, depending on the SRx units, to further decentralise operations and ensure efficient data handling. One should note that the provided architecture for distributed sensing in Figure 3-1 represents a generalised framework that encompasses both monostatic and bistatic configurations, which have traditionally served as the foundational models for sensing systems. By extending beyond these legacy configurations, the distributed approach enables more flexible and adaptive sensing capabilities, leveraging spatially diverse sensor nodes to enhance coverage, resilience, and performance. This generalisation allows for seamless integration of monostatic and bistatic principles while also accommodating more complex, networked sensing paradigms, ultimately broadening the scope and efficiency of modern sensing applications. The specifications for supported devices are given in Table 3-3.

Table 3-3: Device specifications of Contribution #P-1.

	BS	UE	Other devices	Fusion Centre and Processing Centres

Number of Devices	One/multiple (Monostatic/bi-static)	One/Multiple	RIS (optionally) as well as standard 4G/5G devices.	CSePF and LSePFs
Performs Sensing	Yes	Optionally	No	N/A
Sensing measurements	RSSI, SNR, AoA, AoD, ToF	AoA, AoD, SNR, RSSI, ToF,	AoA and AoD for RIS	All existing measurement at BS or UE.
Sensing type	Active or passive	Active or passive	No sensing at RIS, active (in terms or reconfiguration) reflector	N/A
Local sensing processing	Yes	Optional	No (for RIS)	Yes
Computational capabilities	Processing / caching	Processing / caching	No	Processing
Power consumption	Constant supply	Constant supply	Sparse supply/near-passive	Constant supply

The proposed approach and methodology to achieve a distributed architecture for message and protocol exchange build upon classical sensing schemes and centralised processing frameworks. By extending these traditional methodologies to incorporate distributed sensing, the proposed system eliminates the bottlenecks associated with centralisation. This transition involves reengineering the classical sensing architecture to support non-centralised sensing operations and incorporating all necessary message exchanges to ensure effective coordination and data sharing among distributed nodes. This methodology retains the proven strengths of classical systems while integrating advanced techniques for distributed collaboration, making it feasible to operate efficiently in complex and dynamic environments. The resulting architecture is designed to enable seamless, scalable, and adaptive sensing, pushing the boundaries of traditional system capabilities.

For the messaging exchange sequence in Figure 3-1, step 2 needs to be updated if optimised sensing is considered:

- a) **Resource allocation:** After collecting information, SeMF allocates power, time, and frequency resources dynamically based on task priority and requirements (e.g., high priority for safety-critical tasks like collision avoidance or vulnerable road user tracking, as well as latency constraints).
- b) **Beam optimisation:** Beams are tailored to the target’s location and trajectory, considering sensing task requirement and priorities.
- c) **Data representation:** For different task requirements and node capabilities, corresponding data representation is predefined based on task-specific requirements and then dynamically adapted to real-time network and task conditions. E.g., using low-budget for non-critical data and high-budget for high-priority tasks.

Figure 3-2: Flow-chart for optimised sensing.

This approach, described in Figure 3-2, contains the crucial steps that need to take place in each implementation of this protocol, as well as its variations presented in the rest of this section. Each step highlights design choices that concern the concrete implementation. Protocols that are centred around specific components (e.g., data representation and beam design) are presented in the following of this section, while resource allocation algorithms are the focus of the next section.

Operational Benefits and Integration

The potential results of this distributed message exchange scheme are transformative, as they facilitate and accelerate decision-making processes in environments where delays can have significant consequences. By reducing communication bottlenecks and leveraging real-time data from distributed sources, the proposed architecture enables rapid responses to critical scenarios. Fast decision-making is particularly crucial in time-sensitive applications, where delays directly impact outcomes. Furthermore, as the system is deployed and practiced in real-world conditions, additional benefits are expected to emerge, including the discovery of optimised protocols, enhanced fault tolerance, and the ability to adapt to unforeseen challenges. These advancements have the potential to redefine the standards of performance and efficiency in distributed sensing systems.

Related Dissemination and Relation to other 6G-DISAC Contributions

An initial version of this protocol has been presented in Deliverable [6GDISAC-D22] of this Project. Additionally, contributions #A-4, #B-10, #B-11, #B-12, #B-13, #B-14, #B-15, #C-2, #O-5 make use of this protocol in deploying their respective algorithms. Finally, an initial version of the message exchange for sensing has been published in (while being under review for IEEE Wireless Communications Magazine):

E. Calvanese Strinati, G. C. Alexandropoulos, N. Amani, M. Crozzoli, G. Madhusudan, S. Mekki, F. Rivet, V. Sciancalepore, P. Sehier, M. Stark, and H. Wymeersch, "Towards distributed and intelligent integrated sensing and communications for 6G networks," IEEE Wireless Communications, vol. 32, no. 1, pp. 60–67, February 2025.

3.1.2 Contribution #P-2: Sensing with Connected Devices

Motivations and Challenges

In Section 3.1.1, the protocol for bistatic and multistatic sensing assumes known Tx and Rx positions. However, in practical deployments, connected UEs can also assist in sensing tasks. Practical UE positioning methods have been outlined in [3GPP25], where Round-Trip-Time (RTT), angle estimation (i.e., Downlink (DL) Angle of Departure (AoD) or Uplink (UL) Angle of Arrival (AoA)), Time-Difference-of-Arrival (TDoA), and sidelink positioning can be implemented. With SeMF playing a key role here, coordinating hybrid positioning (e.g., combining Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) and terrestrial measurements) while potentially fusing sensing

Figure 3-3: Illustration of sensing with connected devices.

data from reference nodes (e.g., Positioning Reference Units (PRUs)) can be carried out. However, the sensing and positioning scenarios may occur at the same time, enabling joint sensing and positioning. By leveraging UE measurements (e.g., RTT, AoA) alongside SRx data, enhanced sensing performance can be achieved through information fusion.

Deployment Scenario

The deployment scenario can be found in Figure 3-3. In addition to the BS SRxs, the received signals at UE can also be used for sensing purposes. The supported device specifications are given in Table 3-4.

Table 3-4: Device specifications of Contribution #P-2.

	BS	UE	Other devices	Fusion Centre
Number of Devices	One/multiple (Monostatic/bi-static)	One/Multiple	No	CSePF and LSePFs
Performs Sensing	Yes	No	N/A	N/A
Sensing measurements	AoA, AoD, TDoA	AoA, AoD, TDoA	N/A	All measurement at BS or UE.
Sensing type	active or passive	N/A	N/A	N/A
Local processing	Yes	Optional	N/A	Yes
Computational capabilities	Processing / caching	Processing	N/A	Processing
Power Consumption	Constant supply	Sparse supply	N/A	Constant supply

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

Based on the protocol described in Section 3.1.1, a connected device also performs localisation (and calibration if needed) and bistatic/multi-static sensing at the same time. The updated parts are as follows (also highlighted in red in Figure 3-4):

- Step 2: UE will be part of the SRxs to assist sensing tasks.
- Step 8/10: the sensing algorithm needs to be updated into a joint sensing and localisation/calibration algorithm.
- Step 9/11/12: in addition to sensing results, localisation and calibration results will be performed.

The protocol can also be extended to UL scenarios with BSs and other UEs as SRxs. Note that step 2 needs to coordinate STxs to avoid interference.

Operational Benefits and Integration

The benefits of this protocol instantiation are largely equivalent to those of Section 3.1.1. However, in contrast to the protocol previously presented for non-connected devices, the major changes are highlighted in red in the message exchange chart below. The connected UEs also participate in the sensing process (Step 2), and the overall procedure now offers multiple functionalities, including localisation and calibration for the connected devices (Steps 9-12). Such information is treated in a similar manner to the pure sensing information of Section 3.1.1, where both local and centralised processing take place, depending on the system variation.

Figure 3-4: Message chart for sensing with connected devices.

Relation to Other 6G-DISAC Contributions

The following contributions utilise this protocol in the deployment of their algorithmic approaches: #A-3, #A-5, #B-3, #B-4, #B-8, #O-8.

3.1.3 Contribution #P-3: Control and Exploitation of RISs

Motivations and Challenges

RIS nodes are widely considered to be major technological enablers for ISAC, owing to their capability to alter and control the propagation environment. In this regard, while the capabilities and potentials of RISs are well understood, their integration into network architectures is still under study. In particular, the design of network protocols exploited to transfer control messages such as, e.g., optimised RIS configurations or, synchronisation messages when it comes to *autonomous* (or *hybrid*) RISs, which are equipped with special components allowing local sensing of the propagation environment [ADS+22]. In the following, we therefore propose a network protocol that is applicable to both reconfigurable after control or autonomously reconfigurable devices. Moreover, from the energy budget point of view, RIS devices may be nearly passive, active, or hybrid, and therefore the challenge lies in developing a network protocol that can support all such heterogeneous solutions.

Figure 3-5: RIS-aided distributed ISAC network.

Deployment Scenario

A distributed ISAC scenario is considered within a single cell, with a BS acting as both SRx and STx in uplink and downlink (see also Table 3-5 for device details), respectively. One or multiple UEs (SRx(s)), one or multiple targets (ST(s)), an SeMF and a CSePF are also present in the network core, as depicted in Figure 3-5.

Table 3-5: Device specifications of Contribution #P-3.

	BS	UE	RIS	Fusion Centre
Number of Devices	One	One/Multiple	One/Multiple	One
Performs Sensing	Yes	Yes	Yes/No	Yes

Sensing measurements	SNR, AoA, ToA	SNR, AoA, ToA	SNR, AoA, ToA	SNR, AoA, ToA
Sensing type	Active, semi-active	Passive	Active, passive, semi-active	Active, semi-active
Local processing	Yes	No	Yes/No	Yes
Computational capabilities	processing/caching	caching	Minimal processing	Processing/caching
Power Consumption	Constant supply	Constant supply	Nearly- or fully-passive	Constant supply

Figure 3-6: Message exchange chart for RIS-aided distributed ISAC.

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

In this contribution, a network architecture is developed, along with the associated control protocols, for DISAC. In particular, starting from existing RIS control plane methods [RISE-D26], a DISAC system is considered with both autonomous and *controlled* RISs. In both cases, the RIS device is in direct communication with the RIS Controller (RIS-C). However, in the case of controlled RISs, the RIS-C is located within the network and the connection with the BS is then not a wireless link but rather a logical one. Whereas, in the case of autonomous (a.k.a. hybrid) RISs the RIS-C is co-located with the actual physical RIS device, and it acts as LSePF, thereby providing sensing functions.

Operational Benefits and Integration

As shown in Figure 3-6, a message exchange protocol is proposed for the case of communication and/or sensing with a UE (left part), or with a target (right part). We remark that the figure is intended for the case of controlled RIS device. However, in the case of autonomous RISs, the RIS-C is co-located with the RIS device, and therefore the two corresponding columns collapse into a single one. The shown message exchanges are then valid in both cases.

This protocol with its two variations is designed to support the use of RIS devices either with integrated controller and sensing capabilities or with controller physically placed on the network. As a result, both autonomous and controllable operations are supported, which opens possibility for distributed orchestration approaches.

Relation to other 6G-DISAC Contributions

This contribution may serve as the basic network protocol employed in RIS-aided ISAC methods developed in WP3 of this project. In particular, contributions #A-2, #B-1, #B-2, #B-6, #B-7, #O-2, #O-3, #O-4, #O-1, #O-6 make use of this messaging exchange during their deployment.

3.1.4 Contribution #P-4: Reduced Beam Searching for Sensing-Aided Beamforming

Motivations and Challenges

To perform effective SAC, the involved devices typically exchange pilot signals for position, sensing, and channel estimation at pre-defined and equally spaced intervals. This simplifies the protocol structure, however, it may suffer from much denser control plane utilisation than what

(a) Frame of the dynamically spaced pilot protocol in UL and DL. (Top) conventional communication protocol where channel estimation is performed per Transmission Time Interval (TTI); (Bottom) proposed communication protocol where pilot estimation takes places according to the effective beam coherence time, which changes dynamically based on the beamforming loss.

(b) The proposed non-uniform coordinate grid on the xy plane where the UE moves. The spacing between the target positions (red asterisks) increases with distance, as well as with the angle with respect to the antenna broadside. The blue circle encapsulates the points ultimately selected for beam sweeping.

Figure 3-7 Non uniform channel frame and beam searching locations of the proposed framework.

is actually needed to guarantee satisfactory performance. Indeed, for Line of Sight (LoS)-dominant conditions, the beamforming losses observed by users due to misalignment of beamforming-target and actual user position depend principally on the users’ movement patterns and antenna’s beam width, meaning that for wide lobes and moderate movement, sending pilots too often becomes unnecessary. The limitations of fixed-structure protocols become even more pronounced when multiple users need to be time-scheduled, or when the users transition from the near-field to the far-field region.

Table 3-6: Device specifications of Contribution #P-4.

	BS	UE	Other Devices	Fusion Centre
Number of Devices	One	One/Multiple	No	At the BS

Performs Sensing	Yes	No	N/A	N/A
Sensing measurements	CSI	SNR	N/A	N/A
Sensing type	Active	Passive	N/A	N/A
Local processing	Yes	Yes (minimal)	N/A	N/A
Computational capabilities	pro- cessing/cach- ing	caching	N/A	N/A
Power Consumption	Constant supply	Sparse supply	N/A	N/A

Deployment Scenario

Let us consider an ISAC system where a form of ELAA BS, acting as an STx serves multiple users supporting both communication and sensing functionalities (SRxs). The users are scheduled in Time-Division Multiple Access (TDMA) fashion. When the pilot phase is initiated, the BS performs beam sweeping by steering its beams toward different locations. The location where the target device reports the highest beamforming gain is reported to the SeMF, which treats the corresponding beamfocusing target position as an estimate of the users' position (see also Table 3-6).

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

Leveraging the fine-grained beamforming capabilities of large-element antenna BSs, precisely a Dynamic Metasurface Antenna (DMA), an analysis is being carried out of the relative beamforming losses due to position misalignment. Especially in the near-field regime, geometrical bounds are derived for the area where each user maintains a pre-determined signal gain threshold. The bounds are dependent on previous estimates of the users' positions and velocities, that are kept by the SePF. Having those at its disposal, the SePF calculates both the expected time, after which the served user is expected to drop below its desired gain, as well as the most likely candidate positions of the user at this time. A notification signal is then sent to the SRx that the next pilot transmission/position estimation frame will take place. It is noted that both the time intervals between pilot transmissions, as well as the candidate search positions are highly unequally spaced in time and space, respectively. Illustration of these phenomena are given in Figure 3-7. The corresponding protocol for a single sensing client is detailed in Figure 3-8. The SeMF is responsible for determining the appropriate time interval based on expected KPI degradation, after which the localisation information is expected to be outdated and thus triggers the repetition of the procedure.

Results and Discussion

The derived methodology comprises of the dynamic protocol definition, as well as basic functionalities for Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) optimisation and position estimation leveraging the beamforming capabilities of the DMA. Those schemes are compared to an existing DMA localisation approach from literature with a fixed protocol frame structure, as presented in the methodology of [GA25]. The main results are shown in Figure 3-9, where the average relative beamforming gain and its 90-th percentile error bars over time are plotted on the left y-axis. Solid blue and dashed black lines correspond respectively to a tracking algorithm utilising the protocol and

Figure 3-8: Message exchange sequence for Rx tracking with dynamic time intervals and beam focusing locations.

a baseline of a standard fixed-scheme protocol. The right vertical axis in red includes the values of the average estimation intervals for both schemes. While both approaches offer largely comparative performance in terms of beamforming gains, the great benefit brought by the dynamic frame protocol is illustrated on the right-side axes as the distance of the SRx from the STx increases. The average estimation intervals of the proposed protocol are much larger, indicating that there is a great reduction in the TTIs used for pilot transmissions.

Related Dissemination and Relation to other 6G-DISAC Contributions

The algorithmic aspects relevant to this protocol and the performance benefits in terms of sensing accuracy have been investigated under contributions #B-5 and #C-3 of [6GDISAC-D31], where bounds are also derived on sampling ranges and time intervals to guarantee a predefined SNR level. The protocol contribution of this deliverable addresses the benefits in terms of system overhead and discusses the concrete implementation details under the 6G-DISAC architecture. The methodology is published in:

P. Gavriilidis and G. C. Alexandropoulos, "Near-field beam tracking with extremely massive dynamic metasurface antennas," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, to appear, 2025.

3.1.5 Contribution #P-5: Dual-Beam RIS-Integrated Protocol

Motivations and Challenges

Relying on spatially distributed sensing RISs and sensing nodes, moving passive objects can be detected and even localised/tracked in an opportunistic manner, by monitoring the transitory shadowing-induced fluctuations observed on the received power measured with respect to ambient sources present in a dense radio environment [6GDISAC-D31] (Section 5.2.3). However, integrating these sensing functionalities in the context of mmWave communication networks comes along with specific challenges in terms protocol design, which are inherent to the opportunistic and distributed natures of the sensing approach. These challenges typically concern the

Figure 3-9: Comparative performance of proposed dynamic frame protocol for SAC and a fixed structure approach.

control and configuration of both RISs and sensing nodes, so that they can all operate in a synchronous and coordinated way but also the exchange/fusion of space-time coherent sensing information from the sensing nodes, as well as the coexistence at these nodes of sensing and parallel/background data communication operations, aiming at limiting their mutual impact.

Deployment Scenario

The physical deployment supporting this protocol proposal is quite similar to that in [6GDISAC-D31] (Section 5.2.3), which comprises at least one so-called sensing node and at least one dual-beam sensing RIS. However, while distributed sensing is considered to be relatively independent and agnostic with respect to the underlying communication context in [6GDISAC-D31], it is herein assumed that the detection functionality must be performed in-band and integrated in the framework of a dense mmWave communication network. This prevents from deploying too specific sensing entities in the environment, while making opportunistic use of the communication nodes already distributed in the environment. Accordingly, depending on whether UL, DL, or even sidelink communications are considered, each sensing node shall also play the role of a standard UE or BS, which not only measures the received power of ambient non-coherent sources (reflected by the sensing RIS) for opportunistic detection purposes, but also needs to receive and demodulate other signals from communicating peers.

Besides, multiple spatially distributed sources are assumed to emit and/or scatter signals in the environment being sensed (i.e., around each sensing RIS). Such sources can be passive scattering objects, or active sources deliberately emitting radio signals, including unintentional interferers involved in nearby communications (i.e., UEs in UL or BSs in DL). Even if the envisaged sensing function relies mostly on differential received power measurements (and hence by definition, on non-coherent processing) at the sensing node, the sensed sources could also consist of coordinated nodes (i.e., coordinated with sensing), hence benefitting from overall network synchronisation so as to ease the space-time scheduling of sensing operations.

Finally, each dual-beam sensing RIS associated with a sensing node has at least one programmable “input” beam (i.e., the so-called sensing beam). This input beam is used to scan the radio environments in specific angular sectors, therefrom, reflecting the signal power integrated from non-coherent sources in those sectors using its “output” beam (i.e., the reflecting beam), which advantageously points towards the sensing node. Note that even in the case where multiple RISs are associated with the same sensing nodes (e.g., following a time-sharing approach to schedule their respective beam scanning operations), the spatially distributed nature of the sensing operations is preserved as the system still relies on multi-site sensing operations.

In Figure 3-10 (a), an illustrative example for the corresponding physical deployment is provided, where one sensing node BS1 associated with one single RIS#1 is also communicating in UL with a UE (i.e., in a concurrent manner with the sensing task), while other UEs and BSs in its immediate vicinity are used as ambient sources of opportunity (i.e., STxs), which can contribute to the detection of a moving passive target (vehicle). In Figure 3-10 (b), a variant to this first deployment scenario is also shown, where multiple RISs are associated with sensing node BS1, which is still communicating in UL with the same UE as before. The overall device specifications are given in Table 3-7.

Figure 3-10: Physical network deployment variants for distributed ISAC with dual-beam reflective RISs for the cooperative non-coherent sensing of passive targets (i.e., device-free localisation through Rx power monitoring); Examples shown with one RIS (a) or multiple RISs (b) associated with each sensing node (assuming BSs as sensing nodes SRxs).

Protocol Option 1a: Sequential Sensing and Data Communication (Ex. with 1 RIS and 1 BS)

(a)

Protocol Option 1b: Simultaneous Sensing and UL Data Communication (Ex. with 1 RIS and 1 BS)

(b)

Figure 3-11: Message exchange chart variants for distributed ISAC with dual-beam reflective RISs for the cooperative non-coherent sensing of passive targets (~ device-free localisation through Rx power monitoring); Example shown with a BS as main sensing node (SRx).

Table 3-7: Device specifications of Contribution #P-5.

	BS	UE	Other Devices	Fusion Centre
Number of Devices	One/Multiple	One/Multiple	One/Multiple RISs, with at least one directional input beam (but preferably dual-beam)	1 (at SeMF/SePF on network side, or at LSePF co-located with the sensing node), for the multi-RIS cooperative localisation of passive targets

Performs Sensing	Yes	Optional	Through beam sweeping	No
Sensing measurements	RSRP/RSSI/SINR	Optionally, RSRP/RSSI/SINR	No (RIS in reflect mode)	No
Sensing type	Active or passive	Active or passive	Active	N/A
Local processing	Yes	Optional	No	N/A
Computational capabilities	Processing/caching	Processing (optional storage)	No	High capabilities for processing and storage
Power Consumption	Constant supply	Constant supply	Nearly- or fully-passive	Constant supply

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

In compliance with the general 6G-DISAC architecture, the proposed protocol has been designed to support the following tasks and requirements:

1. Depending on local/temporary needs, the SeMF may decide to launch new sensing operations and accordingly, trigger and configure a set of cooperative sensing nodes in Rx (e.g., BSs at specific locations), which hence serve as SRx nodes.
2. Dedicated sensing RISs must be associated to the previous sensing nodes and configured through the network, by means of their respective RIS-Cs, so that reflected signals from ambient sources can be received by these sensing nodes (SRx nodes), in a synchronous manner with respect to the RIS beam scanning operations.
3. Optionally, the SeMF may also trigger and configure other network nodes (e.g., BSs in DL and UEs in UL) to activate their transmission activity, so that they can serve as coordinated ambient sources (i.e., as STx nodes). Otherwise, already established in-band communications (i.e., in a steady-state network regime independent from sensing operations) could still be exploited as uncoordinated ambient sources too.
4. Optionally, the sensing nodes involved as SRx in detection/localisation activities can be engaged in parallel communications with respect to other communication nodes from the same network, which can be scheduled together with the sensing operations, according to sequential (i.e., time sharing) or concurrent (i.e., simultaneous) schemes.
5. Sensing data issued by the LSePFs of different sensing nodes SRx (e.g., received power measurements as a function of time and RIS angular sectors, Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) of the latter, or detected occupied angular sectors directly...) can be shared and fused through a CSePF (or possibly, a LSePF), for further processing (e.g., fusion of angular information for the 2D positioning/tracking of the detected mobile passive obstacles/blockers). The latter will then push the resulting information to the SeMF for higher-level analysis/processing.
6. Based on the scene analysis (i.e., instantaneous or predicted positions of all BSs, UEs, and detected mobile blockers), the SeMF may guarantee new obstruction-free data communications (with or without handover) over specific links and configure the concerned communication nodes accordingly (typically, BSs for DL communications).

Results and Discussion

Figure 3-11 illustrates the message sequence charts corresponding to the previous protocol requirements for one single sensing node SRx and one associated RIS, for both sequential (a) and concurrent/simultaneous (b) sensing and communication operations, keeping in mind that

the extension to multiple sensing SRxs in the considered distributed sensing context is straightforward.

Relation to other 6G-DISAC Contributions

While this protocol proposal was intended to support the integration of the distributed sensing method (Contribution #B-10) introduced in [6GDISAC-D31] in a mmWave network context, related research aspects regarding radio resource allocation at link level under several sequential or simultaneous protocol variants (and the resulting trade-offs between communication and sensing performances) will be accounted hereafter in Section 4.1 (Contribution #O-1). Beyond, other related contributions related to the orchestration of DISAC tasks at network level in the same scenario/context will be reported in next deliverable D4.2.

3.1.6 Contribution #P-6: Data Processing and Data representation

Motivations and Challenges

This is a prolongation of the enabler regarding data processing and data representation in [6GDISAC-D22] (Section 2.1). It is also closely related to the discussion in Section 3.1.1 on distributed sensing protocols. As mentioned in the above references, sensing data processing can take place locally at the sensing receiver, at the edge and at the network core. Also, the level of processing done locally depends on the capabilities and limitations at the sensing receiver particularly when it is a UE. Hence the data to be exchanged between a sensing receiver and the CSePF, also called data representation [ZLZ+22], will vary according to the needs of the sensing service and the capabilities of the entities involved in the processing. This obviously has an impact on the protocol as the two ends of the sensing processing (for example local sensing receiver and the CSePF) need to agree on the data representation used for the exchange of sensing data.

Deployment Scenario

As illustrated in Section 3.1.1, multiple STXs and SRXs are spread out over the sensing service area. Local processing may be performed on some SRXs (LSePF). Results are sent to CSePF for fusion.

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

As described in [6GDISAC-D22] (Section 3.2.1), the procedure may be described as follows.

1. A sensing request is received by the SeMF from an Application Function with the service requirements and a Sensing Service Area (SSA).
2. As shown in Section 3.1.1, selection of potential sensing nodes for the SSA is performed by SeMF.
3. The SeMF chooses a data representation based on the sensing service requirements. The SeMF configures the selected nodes with shared sensing configuration, the data representation to be used, the refresh rates.
4. The LSePF after executing the local processing with send the sensing report to CSePF using the data representation chosen in step 3.

Results and Discussion

A preliminary version of this protocol extension has been proposed above. However, the mapping from sensing service requirements to data representation choices is work in progress. An update will be provided for final version of this specification.

Dissemination and Relation to other 6G-DISAC Contributions

The protocol presented in this contribution extends the data representation discussion of [6GDISAC-D22]. A preliminary version of the protocol has been submitted as discussion topic alongside other data representation aspects in ETSI ISG ISAC as:

ETSI, "Data Representation for Sensing: An Overview and Challenges", ISC(24)000118, ISG ISAC, June 24, 2024.

3.2 Contribution #P-7: Semantic Waveform Components in DISAC Protocols

Motivations and Challenges

The integration of Semantic Communication (SemCom) at the physical layer is opening dynamic directions in 6G, enabling adaptive and goal-oriented transmission strategies. While early developments have explored its interplay with MIMO, beamforming, RIS, ISAC, and interference management, waveform design remains largely overlooked. This limits the potential for semantic-aware encoding and joint optimisation, as waveforms are still treated as passive carriers of bits rather than instruments of meaning.

To address this, [HHC+25] introduces Orthogonal Semantic Sequency Division Multiplexing (OSSDM), a semantic-aware waveform design that leverages the robustness of SemCom to reduce power, bandwidth, and time usage. Unlike conventional waveforms optimised for bit-level accuracy or throughput, OSSDM targets interpretability and resilience to semantically irrelevant distortions. The design objective shifts toward maximising Semantic Spectral Efficiency (SSE), measured as correctly interpreted semantic content per Hz per second [YQZ+22].

The implication of this contribution on the protocol structures elaborated in this chapter reflects in an enhancement of the communication protocol framework, due to the introduction of meaning-driven transmissions carrying only the most relevant data. This shift enables each protocol stage to prioritise content based on semantic importance rather than raw fidelity. In the context of D-ISAC, the OSSDM waveform aligns naturally with the protocol structure proposed in the contribution of Section 3.1.1, particularly in steps 5 to 10, where connected node pairs engage in selective exchange. Here, OSSDM allows the system to disregard inconsequential distortions and focus transmission resources on elements essential for shared understanding or joint tasks. This facilitates more efficient integration of sensing and communication without compromising interpretability, supporting semantic fidelity where it matters most.

Deployment Scenario

The deployment scenario for this contribution, can be a generalization of the one proposed in [6GDISAC-D31] (Section 4.1). The existence of an entity is assumed, which is endowed with computation and communication capabilities, transmitting sensing information, once the received sensing data has been locally semantically processed and encoded. For example, the protocol in Section 3.1.1 (Figure 3-1) can be also applied for the proposed contribution, in particular steps 6-8. A Sensing Rx (SRx) entity can transmit to an LSePF semantic symbols instead of raw sensed data. Furthermore, the sensor Sensing Tx (STx), if enabled with the computation and communication capabilities, can process and compress itself sensing data locally, before sending information to the receiver. In this contribution, the sensing process is not covered but planned for next deliverables.

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

The OSSMD methodology operates through a tightly integrated signalling exchange between the architecture nodes, coordinating sensing and communication tasks across spatially distributed agents. As depicted in Figure 3-12, upon receiving a semantic sensing request from the client, the SeMF resolves the spatial and temporal sensing requirements into a specific tasking

Figure 3-12: Integration of OSSDM as part of the DISAC sensing protocol.

of TX-RX pairs. This includes selecting appropriate nodes with view of the sensing region. The CSePF manages encoder selection, waveform codebook allocation, and graph fusion configurations suitable for the current environment and task. These choices are informed by prior sensing maps and potentially contextual priors over object presence or motion models. This step (Step 4) is needed to align the semantic content (primarily in terms of neural network weights) between the communicating LSePFs and the CSePF, and might be skipped in future protocol instantiation if the LSePFs have sufficient caching and storage capabilities.

Next, the CSePF communicates with the relevant LSePFs to deploy the waveform strategy. Each LSePF applies the assigned semantic encoder and waveform modulator, adapted to local channel and hardware constraints. The encoded waveform is generated and emitted by the designated TX, optionally passing through reconfigurable RISs. At the RX side, local signal capture is followed by semantic inference directly on the received waveform, without full reconstruction. The local predictions are then sent back to the CSePF.

The core of OSSMD lies in the structured fusion of these semantic reports using graph-based reasoning. The CSePF maintains a dynamic graph representation where each node corresponds to an RX or local viewpoint, and edges encode spatial correlation or reliability priors. Fusion proceeds via belief propagation or learned graph decoding, integrating weak and potentially noisy local inferences into a globally consistent semantic map. The final result is returned to the client as a semantic field over the observed region. This sequence prioritises message-driven interactions, emphasising modular separation between waveform generation, semantic coding, and graph-based inference. It supports heterogeneous network topologies, partial observability, and task-adaptive sensing through real-time coordination across the control layers.

Results and Discussion

The OSSDM framework is based on the orthogonal Walsh function basis, which facilitates energy-efficient digital-to-RF signal conversion and outperforming OFDM in power efficiency. A key departure from traditional architectures is that semantic encoding is performed directly at

the waveform level. This not only enhances SSE but also supports the simultaneous optimisation of multiple transmission objectives within a single waveform structure.

The proposed method is configurable, allowing for a controlled degradation of the waveform in exchange for achieving an adequate level of semantic understanding at the receiver. This trade-off enables more efficient use of system resources.

Experimental results confirm significant improvements in semantic reconstruction quality, offering added benefits that go beyond the capabilities of standard source and channel coding techniques, as shown in [6GDISAC-D31] (Section 4.1).

Relation to other 6G-DISAC Contributions

This study relates to the Contribution #A-1 detailed in [6GDISAC-D31].

3.3 Contribution #P-8: Learning-based protocols

Learning-based methods are becoming a core enabler in ISAC, supporting adaptive behaviour across a wide range of scenarios. By leveraging patterns in data, these methods enable systems to dynamically tune parameters, predict environmental changes, and optimise joint sensing-communication strategies. Approaches such as online learning and continual model refinement allow for rapid adaptation to local context, while collaborative training across distributed agents supports generalisation and robustness in more complex environments. Federated approaches build on this by enabling multiple devices or nodes to train shared models without the need to centralise raw data. Each participant updates its local model based on locally observed information, and only the resulting parameters or gradients are exchanged. This not only mitigates privacy concerns but also significantly reduces communication overhead. Together, learning and federation provide the algorithmic backbone for ISAC systems to evolve over time, operate efficiently at scale, and maintain responsiveness across diverse and changing conditions.

To fully take advantage of the promising benefits of ML approaches, protocols are needed to handle trust, synchronisation, and resource allocation, particularly in deployments involving heterogeneous devices or intermittent connectivity. These include aspects on the coordination of training rounds and model updates, consistency management across dynamic topologies, and the alignment of learning objectives with sensing and communication functions. The contribution of this subsection highlights the key aspects of coordinating autonomous multi-antenna devices that are capable for local learning, storage, and decision making, toward facilitating predefined user requirements.

Motivations and Challenges

In distributed architectures, where a cooperative optimisation scheme is applied to optimise the (co-)operation of all network entities, typically, large overheads are observed in terms of data sharing, control messaging, and feedback signalling. This problem is only exacerbated when semi-autonomous deep learning agents are spread over the network to control the various devices. In such cases, not only do input matrices need to be transmitted to the local processing units, but more importantly, the employed DNNs typically exchange their parameters, which could be in the order of millions to billions to enable federated learning schemes.

Deployment Scenario

Consider a system where multiple multi-antenna devices (namely, ELAAs), acting first as SRxs, while needing to determine their beamforming patterns to enable an ISAC task for one or more RXs. Each device is assumed to be equipped with (i) signal reception equipment; (ii) out-of-band transmission and reception capabilities; (iii) local processing and storage units (LSePF), and (iv) antenna pattern reconfiguration mechanisms. The STx coordinates the sensing measurements, while it also coordinates the out-of-band measurements of the devices, enabling co-configuration. The objective of the system is to perform channel estimation and environment

mapping, while also offering communication service to the user. In fact, the multi-antenna devices may exploit their sensing results into determining effective sensing-aided beamforming strategies. The overall deployment for device specifications of Table 3-8 is given in Figure 3-13.

Table 3-8: Device specifications of Contribution #P-8.

	BS	UE	Other Devices	Fusion Centre
Number of Devices	One	Multiple	Multi-antenna beamformers (ELAAs)	No
Performs Sensing	Yes	No	Yes	N/A
Sensing measurements	CSI	Any	CSI	N/A
Sensing type	Active	Passive	Active	N/A
Local processing	Yes	Yes (minimal)	Yes	N/A
Computational capabilities	DNN storage, training, inference	Minimal	DNN storage, training, inference	N/A
Power Consumption	Constant supply	Sparse supply	Constant supply	N/A

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

The first stage of the approach involves the STx sending pilots toward the SRxs for each one to perform their own local channel parameter estimation. To account for the co-existence of multiple devices, the pilots are distributed along the time, spatial, and frequency domains. Each SRx determines their individual channel parameters, which are stored in the storage unit of their

Figure 3-13: Setup for autonomous configuration of ELAAs/BS, each one associated with its local DNN. Model parameters are shared among them before communication and sensing transmissions take place.

LSePF. Next those parameters are compressed through a pre-defined process and only a small encoding of them is broadcast to all the SRxs and the STx in an out-of-band control channel. All of the SRxs and the STx then proceed to individually define their own beamforming strategies toward serving the communication user, based on their local channel measurements and the received information. The proposed signalling protocol alleviates the need for large data exchange of coordinating beamforming users, since local processing takes place at the edge device and only information that is helpful toward the beam-steering operation. The nature of this information is left as implementation defined. The overall time sequence is given in Figure 3-14. Two stages of pilot exchanges are needed: During the first stage (Step 5), initial pilot exchange takes place so that all ELAAs acting as TXs and RXs use the collected information to update their individual antenna configurations. The configurations are exchanged either in the form of codebook indices, individual values, or as DNN parameter vectors. Each LSePF receives all incoming signals and re-determines its final configuration. Then, the rest of the process is detailed as the general protocols of the previous sections.

Related Dissemination and Relation to other 6G-DISAC Contributions

A system making use this protocol has been proposed in the following paper:

G. Stamatelis, K. Stylianopoulos, G. C. Alexandropoulos “Multi-Branch Attention Convolutional Neural Network for Online RIS Configuration with Discrete Responses: A Neuroevolution Approach”, in *IEEE Transactions on Cognitive Communications and Networking*, to appear, 2025.

Additionally, the contribution of Section 4.4 (Contribution #O-9) makes use of this protocol to propose autonomous cooperating RIS devices for ISAC.

Figure 3-14: Time diagram for autonomous ELAA device configuration with local DNNs.

4 Orchestration and Resource Allocation Algorithms for Distributed ISAC Architectures

Orchestration in distributed ISAC systems refers to the intelligent coordination of sensing, communication, and computation across multiple networked entities [LCM+22]. It involves making real-time decisions about resource allocation, task distribution, and system-level trade-offs, thus balancing device capabilities, latency constraints, energy budgets, and application-specific performance targets. As ISAC deployments grow in scale and heterogeneity, orchestration algorithms must handle increasingly complex operating conditions, including dynamic topologies, reconfigurable devices [EZS+20], non-stationary environments, and mixed-criticality workloads.

Effective orchestration requires more than static scheduling; it must incorporate context-awareness, goal-driven behaviour, and the ability to prioritise based on semantic relevance rather than raw data throughput. This includes aligning system operation with high-level intents, e.g., tracking a moving object, maintaining link reliability, or preserving power in constrained nodes. Autonomous operation becomes essential in such settings [CCS+19], enabling local agents to act independently while still contributing to a global objective. This section explores algorithmic approaches to orchestration that address these demands, with a focus on scalability, adaptability, and minimal control overhead in complex ISAC environments.

4.1 Algorithms for Cooperative Multi-Sensor and Multi-Modal Systems

Distributed ISAC architectures increasingly rely on cooperation among multiple sensors of often different modalities to enable robust situational awareness and context-driven adaptability. By integrating diverse sensing sources, systems can exploit complementary strengths and mitigate individual weaknesses, leading to more resilient and accurate perception. Cooperation extends beyond simple data aggregation; it involves joint inference, cross-modality calibration, and task-driven fusion strategies that adapt to environmental dynamics and mission requirements. Enabling this level of coordination demands orchestration algorithms that manage information flow, align sensing objectives, and balance trade-offs between latency, bandwidth, and computational load. This section outlines algorithmic strategies for harnessing multi-sensor cooperation in ISAC, with emphasis on scalable coordination, real-time adaptability, and efficient resource management across distributed nodes. The characteristics of the contributions of this section are detailed in Table 4-1.

Table 4-1: Physical and signal properties of contributions related to cooperative and multi-sensor orchestration DISAC algorithms.

	Contr. #O-1	Contr. #O-2	Contr. #O-3	Contr. #O-4	Contr. #O-5
Physical deployment					
BSs, antennas, and functional use	Multiple multi-antenna BSs acting as STxs and/or SRxs.	Multiple single antenna BSs acting as SRxs (implicit).	Multiple single antenna BSs/APs acting as STxs.	Single multi-antenna BS acting as STx.	Single antenna BS acting as STx.
UEs, antennas, and functional use	Multiple multi-antenna UEs acting as SRxs and/or STxs.	One single antenna UE acting as STx (implicit).	One single-antenna device acting as both STx and SRx.	One single-antenna device acting as SRx.	Single antenna UE acting as SRx.
Passive/active controllable devices in the environment,	Multiple controllable passive dual-beam RISs	Implicit eavesdropper UE acting as SRx	One or multiple controllable passive RISs, acting	One passive controllable RIS, acting as STx	Single reflective metasurface (controlled by ex-

and functional use	acting as power relays.		as SRx and STx		ternal entities) acting as ST
STs	Multiple mobile passive STs.	One static UE (implied)	One static or mobile UE	One static UE	Fixed (passive) multi-antenna ST
Nodes with LSePFs	SRxs	STxs	RISs	N/A	N/A
Nodes relying on CSePF	SRxs	N/A	RISs	RIS controller	STx, SRx
Types of data in the SeMF	N/A	Processed pilots (abstract signals)	Received power	N/A	Received pilots
Wireless requirements					
Type of radio measurements	Received power	N/A	Received power	N/A	Received pilots
Frequency/bandwidth	Frequency agnostic, mmWave preferable.	Agnostic	Agnostic	Agnostic	Frequency agnostic/narrowband
Synchronisation requirements	Time synchronisation between each SRx and its associated RIS	Among SRxs	Between all devices	Between all devices	between STx, SRx
LoS/NLoS conditions	Both LoS and NLoS (LoS between RIS)	Ricean	LoS	LoS	LoS

4.1.1 Contribution #O-1: Link-Level Resource Allocation for the Integration of RIS-Based Passive Objects Sensing in mmWave Communication Networks

Motivation and Challenges

As already discussed in Sec. 3.1.5 from a protocol-oriented standpoint, the integration in a communication network of sensing capabilities relying on spatially distributed reflective RISs arises specific challenges in terms of resource allocation and operating trade-offs. Typically, given the opportunistic nature of the proposed shadowing-based sensing method and the will to mutualise the deployed network resources (i.e., avoiding the use of active nodes uniquely dedicated to sensing), the UEs or BSs involved as SRx nodes can also be engaged in parallel communication links with respect to other communication nodes belonging to the same network. These data communication operations can be scheduled together with the sensing operations, according to sequential (i.e., through time sharing) or concurrent/simultaneous schemes. In the former case, given an imposed resource budget, the time dedicated to sensing will reduce the useful data rate in support of detection performances (e.g., refining spatial resolution), while in the latter case, the RIS reflections may positively impact the Rx power sensitivity for sensing but may also generate harmful interferences with respect to the communication link. In both cases, adequate resource allocation schemes must thus be designed, so that relevant operating trade-

offs can be achieved between communication and sensing performances, at both link and network levels.

Deployment Scenario

The considered physical deployment is adapted from that introduced in Section 3.1.5 and is illustrated in Figure 4-1. The only modification is that the focus is put here on a canonical scenario at link level, with one single dual-beam RIS and one reference communication link under study, which involves the sensing node associated with the sensing RIS. Besides, multiple other UEs and BSs are still considered active in transmission in the environment, acting as STxs and being beneficial – as ambient non-coherent sources- to the envisaged sensing approach. Without loss of generality regarding the investigated resource allocation strategies, it is also assumed that the sensing node is a UE that communicates in DL with its serving BS.

Figure 4-1: Example of link-level RIS-aided deployment scenario considered for the proposed resource allocation and communication-sensing trade-off study, where the UE and ambient sources (i.e., other BSs and UEs from the same dense mmWave network) play respectively the roles of SRx and STx for sensing.

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

For the different protocol variants shown on the figure below (i.e., in both sequential and concurrent/simultaneous schemes), different problems can be stated to trade-off the performance of sensing and communication services by jointly or conditionally optimising a subset of key system parameters (e.g., the time devoted to sensing, the number of RIS elements and hence the input/output gains and beam width, the beam angular resolution or overall span during scanning protocol, etc...), while optimising some predefined utility or objective functions. As possible examples, one objective can consist in scanning a given or a targeted region of space within a certain amount of time, or to maximise a joint utility function of both (calibrated) sensing and communication Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratios (SINRs), or simply the communication SINR (or any other monotonic function of the latter) under the constraint of sensing SINR or sensing resolution (and vice versa). Typically, the sensing may also opportunistically exploit periods of time when the requirements in terms of the communication Quality of Service (QoS) at the UE/sensing node are over-satisfied. In this case, a scheduler can constantly monitor such time windows of opportunity and dynamically estimate an affordable power margin, which indicates somehow how much RIS-induced interference the sensing procedure can deliberately

generate onto the communication while keeping acceptable communication performances. Alternatively, the objective function can also incorporate close-form expressions that explicitly and directly link optimisation parameters with communication-oriented KPIs such as the throughput. Conversely, one can also iteratively improve the sensing performance in a “best effort” way (typically, by gradually increasing the sensing RIS beam gains, but hence the level of induced interference) till the moment the experienced deterioration of the primary BS-UE communication QoS empirically approaches a certain tolerance threshold, in comparison with a priori application requirements. These various optimisation options are currently being explored in the frame of this study.

Figure 4-2: Sequential (a, b) or concurrent (c, d) sensing and data communication services for an exhaustive (a, c) or partial/selective (b, d) “input” beam scanning of the sensing dual-beam RIS over the N possible steering angular sectors.

Results and Discussion

To illustrate the presence of a trade-off at link level between sensing and communication performances in both sequential and concurrent ISAC modes, the simplified scenario of Figure 4-1 has been considered in simulations, where one reference dual-beam RIS exhaustively scans the radio environment by sweeping (in azimuth) its “input” beam over 180° during the sensing period. As shown in Figure 4-2, both sensing and data communication services take place during an overall service frame, which is divided into multiples service time slots of equal durations. In each of those slots, it is assumed that one unique angular sector can be sensed (at most). Accordingly, the number of required slots to cover the 180° space for sensing and hence, the duration of the sensing period itself, can vary significantly depending on the considered angular resolution (i.e., related to the width of the RIS “Input” beam, also referred to as “sector” hereafter). After initialisation and beam training procedures, the reference RIS systematically steers its “Output” beam towards the nearest multi-antenna UE, which is hence chosen to serve as

sensing node. In addition, the latter is associated with the nearest multi-antenna BS for DL communications. The corresponding radio link is used as reference to assess the communication performance. In the sequential ISAC mode, the UE alternatively points the main lobe of its power gain pattern towards its associated RIS during the sensing phase and then towards its serving BS during the DL communication phase. However, in case of concurrent sensing and communication services, it prioritises the DL transmission while listening to the RIS only via its side lobes, similarly to [SDD23]. Finally, irrespective of the selected ISAC mode, the UE is considered to stop receiving some reflected power from the RIS after one exhaustive sensing scan is completed, even though it keeps on communicating with the BS thereafter (i.e., till the end of the current service period).

In this study, following a Monte Carlo (MC) approach, 1000 realisations have been drawn on a service frame consisting of 40 service slots, each having the duration of an Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) frame. For each MC realisation, all the network nodes (incl. all BSs and UEs besides the reference ISAC nodes under evaluation), as well as the fading coefficients applied to all possible physical radio links (incl. Interfering links), are randomly generated. For each realisation though, in the concurrent mode, depending on the current RIS “Input” beam steering, the “instantaneous” communication SINR may vary from one service slot to the next, hence impacting the available DL capacity.

The reference RIS is systematically set at the centre of a 200 m x 200 m area, where BSs and UEs are drawn according to two homogeneous Poisson Point Processes (PPP) with densities of $5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^{-2}$ and $1.25 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^{-2}$, respectively. The network operates at 28 GHz, while the bandwidths for BSs and UEs are set to 300 MHz and 100 MHz, respectively. Finally, all the BSs are supposed to follow an equal power allocation scheme with respect to their associated UEs, with an average total transmit power of 33 dBm.

As shown in Figure 4-3(a), the average capacity of the reference DL communication link over a typical service frame, which is evaluated based on the simulated SINR conditions per service slot and following a similar methodology as in [LSS+23] increases monotonically with the sector width within both sequential and concurrent modes. In the former case, the reason is that finer scanning resolutions (i.e., narrower sectors) imply longer scanning periods, and hence, shorter periods left for DL communications, while in the latter case, narrower RIS “Input” beams come along with higher power gains, and hence, stronger interfering power from the ambient sources (reflected by the RIS to the UE). Besides, as expected and regardless of the considered sensing spatial resolution, the concurrent ISAC mode seems more efficient in terms of resource usage (i.e., given the same amount of time for the service frame). In this mode, the amount of RIS-reflected ambient power collected at the UE from interfering sources is indeed much lower than the useful power received from the BS over the main DL communication link. This is even more significant as the UE systematically steers its main beam towards the BS in the concurrent mode in this study. However, this result can also be mitigated, as the imposed sensing resolution cannot directly reveal the actual detection performance, especially if the detection process is uniquely based on the monitoring of the differential power received at the sensing node (i.e., detecting the temporary shadowing effect induced by a moving passive target with respect to ambient sources) in presence of a largely dominating power contribution over the DL link from the BS. In this case, from a pure sensing standpoint, the interpretation of the power fluctuations induced by the mobile obstacle may indeed be harmed by this dominating BS-UE communication link on the one hand, and by the direct collection (i.e., not reflected by the RIS) of received power from non-coherent sources through the side lobes of the sensing node (i.e., SRx), which can also be seen as interference with respect to the sensing functionality itself (similar to data communications).

As a complementary representation, Figure 4-3(b) illustrates variations of the “instantaneous” DL capacity as a function of the service slot in the concurrent ISAC mode only, for two sensing resolutions and on the same MC realisation. Besides the impact of the chosen sensing resolution on the actual duration of the period when both communication and sensing services are

performed simultaneously, it is also noticed that the useful data rate can be temporarily degraded depending on the current RIS “Input” beam steering angle and power gain (depending on the resolution), as well as on the density and the activity of the interfering sources present in the corresponding angular sector. Knowing that in the alternate ISAC mode the communication phase usually provides a more stable QoS, this underscores the importance of protocol selection to meet both sensing and communication KPIs.

Foreseen extensions to the preliminary study above concern (i) the assessment of sensing-centric KPIs under different scanning protocols – with particular focus on the interference created by the communication operations to the sensing signal, (ii) the design of optimisation-based resources allocation schemes to dynamically/contextually meet the best communication-sensing trade-offs at link level on the one hand; as well as (iii) the network-level orchestration of both communication and sensing tasks in a more complex multi-UE, multi-BS, multi-RIS scenario. The corresponding results shall be accounted for in the next deliverable D4.2.

Figure 4-3: Example of average DL capacity for sequential and concurrent sensing and data communications during a service frame, as a function of the sensing spatial resolution (a) and instantaneous fluctuations of this DL capacity as a function of the service slot.

Relation to other 6G-DISAC Contributions

This study relates to the sensing algorithms #B-10 from [6GDISAC-D31] (Section 5.2.3), as well as to the protocol description #P-5 of Section 3.1.5.

4.1.2 Contribution #O-2: Cooperative Active Hypothesis Testing in the Presence of an Eavesdropper

Motivation and Challenges

Active hypothesis testing and related problems find numerous applications in modern wireless communications and signal processing, including anomaly detection over sensor networks, network traffic monitoring, target or threat detection, visual object search, radar assisted target classification, and RIS-assisted channel estimation. With the rise of IoT applications, researchers and industry practitioners are interested in designing scalable distributed surveillance and estimation strategies, where the computation is conducted in multiple independent heterogeneous devices (agents). Careful design of individual sensing mechanisms along with collaboration protocols is of utmost importance. At the same time, it has been observed that even in encrypted IoT applications, eavesdroppers can accurately estimate sensitive information just by observing device interactions. Finally, it is mathematically proven that collaborative multi-agent decision

making under partial observability is computationally expensive, and optimal tractable solutions in general, cannot be computed.

Cooperative active sensing strategies address the inherent resource intensity of distributed inference. In such systems, agents must not only collect data but also select their sensing actions intelligently under tight energy and communication constraints. Active sensing offers a natural orchestration mechanism by enabling agents to dynamically prioritise the most informative actions, thereby reducing unnecessary measurements and interactions. This selective probing is particularly critical when collaborative decisions must be made under partial observability and adversarial monitoring. Moreover, rapid resolution of the sensing task efficiently uses available resources, as early termination of the inference process directly translates to savings in energy, bandwidth, and computational load.

Deployment Scenario

Consider an environment, in which lightweight IoT sensors monitor an area, e.g., a power plant. Each sensor is placed near a different vulnerable sub-area and detects abnormal activity (e.g., energy leaks, equipment damage, heat). Each agent is a computing node with access to a subset of the sensors. The devices are assumed to have heterogeneous capabilities, so that each device may control different sensors and they are associated with diverse observation distributions. Due to the large number of sensors, processing all observations in real time is not feasible and a careful sensor selection needs to be conducted. At the same time, third party entities eavesdrop on the communication links between the agents and the sensors and try to infer the location of anomalies.

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

A novel deep Neuro-Evolution (NE) framework is developed for multi-agent decision making problems. In this framework, all agents share the same DNN for feature extraction. At the same time each agent has a small stack of linear-ReLU activated layers, entitled the individual branch DNN. At each time instance, it passes its most recent observation through the global extractor and the individual DNN in order to select a sensing action. This action and its corresponding

Figure 4-4: The proposed neural network architecture for NE-based multi-agent cooperation. Each agent passes its belief to the global feature extractor, and then, to its individual branch. The entire architecture can be evolved with typical NE algorithms, such as CoSyNE.

Figure 4-5: Average episode stopping time of single-agent hypothesis testing for different values of the threshold for eavesdropper's posterior detection error probability E .

observations are broadcasted to nearby agents to facilitate reliable distributed inference. All networks are evolved as one architecture with an appropriate fitness function, using popular single-agent NE algorithms. This approach is illustrated schematically in Figure 4-4. The proposed implementation uses the Cooperative Synapse Neuro-Evolution (CoSyNE) [SKA24] algorithm.

Results and Discussion

The distributed scheme outperforms the state-of-the-art multi-agent deep reinforcement learning benchmark, based on Proximal Policy Optimisation (PPO) [SWD+17]. Different synthetic sensor models as well as different numbers of sensors have been considered. As shown in Figure 4-5, where the methods are evaluated based on the number of iterations required so that the eavesdropper's detection error probability drops below a predefined threshold, the developed algorithm succeeds in stopping earlier compared to PPO and the theoretical Chernoff bound. The Extrinsic Jensen Shannon (EJS) strategy achieves earlier stopping rates, however, it often fails to satisfy the privacy threshold. Overall, the algorithm satisfies privacy and accuracy constraints, while achieving shorter stopping times than PPO.

Related Dissemination

This work has been published as:

G. Stamatelis, A. -N. Kanatas, I. Asprogerakas and G. C. Alexandropoulos, "Single- and Multi-Agent Private Active Sensing: A Deep Neuroevolution Approach," 2024 IEEE International Conference on Communications Workshops (ICC Workshops), Denver, CO, USA, 2024, pp. 1036-1041.

4.1.3 Contribution #O-3: Cooperative Localisation of Active Users in Indoor Environment

Motivation and Challenges

In this contribution, control methods for positioning in a smart factory environment is being studied. In particular, a novel positioning approach is introduced, which is tailored for smart factory environments, where Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs) and robots typically rely on relative positioning for navigation due to the absence of GNSS indoors. Such dependence raises safety concerns, particularly as interactions between AGVs and human workers become more frequent, increasing the risk of accidents [CWH+23]. To address these challenges, a localisation strategy leveraging D-MIMO devices mounted on AGVs is proposed, where fixed beacons strategically placed within the environment. The multi-antenna devices on the AGVs (e.g., RIS) act as intelligent relays and are capable of dynamically directing signals toward IoT-tagged objects, including human workers.

Cooperative localisation in distributed indoor environments presents a fundamental orchestration problem: determining which devices should participate in the positioning task, under what

conditions, and with what roles. In smart factory settings, where both mobile agents (such as AGVs equipped with D-MIMO transceivers) and fixed infrastructure (such as strategically placed beacons) are available, the system must continuously decide which subset of devices provides the most relevant information for accurate and timely localisation. The inclusion of RIS-equipped nodes introduces an additional layer of complexity, as their reconfigurable nature allows them to enhance localisation performance only when correctly aligned with active devices and targets. In cluttered and dynamic environments, naive participation by all agents leads to interference, redundant data, and inefficient operation. Effective cooperative schemes instead promote selective engagement, allowing the system to focus its resources on the most informative spatial and temporal configurations. This targeted allocation supports safer interaction between humans and machines, faster localisation updates, and scalable deployment as the number of connected devices increases.

Deployment Scenario

As shown in Figure 4-6, let us consider an indoor environment wherein three fixed beacons are deployed in position $\{x_i, y_i\}_{i=1}^3$, alongside two or more mobile AGV-mounted D-MIMO devices, whose instantaneous position and orientation are denoted as $\{x_{R,i}, y_{R,i}\} \forall i$ and $\theta_{R,i} \forall i$, respectively.

Figure 4-6: Deployment scenario for indoor user localisation with mobile D-MIMO-AGVs and fixed beacons.

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

The proposed approach consists in two major phases:

1. Localisation of the AGV-mounted MIMO devices: this first part involves estimating both the position and the orientation of the devices, by exploiting reference signals sent from the three beacons, whose position in the environment is known. This is done sequentially for all available D-MIMO devices.
2. Localisation of the IoT device, given the estimated D-MIMO-AGV positions: this second part is subdivided into R sub-tasks, where R is the total number of D-MIMO-AGV devices, as
 - 2.1 Based on the result of step 1, the MIMO devices scan the environment by exploiting their precise beamforming capabilities to detect the direction to the IoT device.
 - 2.2 All the collected IoT device position estimates are then fused together by a central entity, which extracts a single position estimate.

Based on step 2.2 above, the need for an intelligent central orchestrator is apparent. Indeed, the sensing information collected by the *R*D-MIMO-AGV devices may be affected by heterogeneous channel conditions, which in turn have an impact on the SNR. Such information then needs to be fused by accounting for different levels of confidence in the sensing data. The design of such network node is foreseen to be included in future deliverables.

Results and Discussion

As shown in Figure 4-7, the performance of the proposed approach is verified in 30x30m indoor environment, wherein the beacons are placed in three different configurations, mainly L-shaped, Triangular-shaped, and Planar (i.e., lying on the same x-z plane), as shown on the left-hand side. Assume that the AGVs are equipped with 10x10 RIS boards. On the right-hand side, the Cumulative probability Density Function (CDF) for each beacon deployment is shown, demonstrating an average localisation error of 5, 3.5, and 2 m, respectively.

Figure 4-7: CDF of the IoT device localisation error for different beacon deployments.

Relation to other 6G-DISAC Contributions

This contribution relates to the contribution #B-6 of [6GDISAC-D31] (Section 5.1.6) and exploits a network protocol as detailed in Section 3.1.3 of this deliverable.

4.1.4 Contribution #O-4: Opportunistic Localisation of Active Users

Motivation and Challenges

In this contribution, opportunistic ISAC with RIS is being studied. While RISs are primarily optimised for communication purposes, their configurations inherently contain valuable spatial information about UE locations. The key challenge lies in extracting this positional data without compromising the RIS’s primary communication optimisation function, while maintaining low computational complexity and power requirements suitable for practical deployment. Unlike existing methods (see, e.g., [AKK+21] – COLoRIS (Localisation-agnostic Smart Surfaces)) employs an artificial intelligence architecture to extract positional information from RIS configurations without interfering with their optimisation process [EDR25]. Then, the extracted information on the UE position through COLoRIS is valuable to ease the orchestration process and limit the waste of resources.

Deployment Scenario

The network consists of a BS or Access Point (AP), an N-antenna RIS and a single UE with unknown position, as shown in Figure 4-8. The BS operates the channel estimation process and communicates the configuration to the RIS controller. Subsequently, the RIS controller exploits the COLoRIS framework to retrieve the user position. The RIS controller can be linked with the orchestrator and the obtained information on the UE may be employed for resource orchestration. The system operates in both indoor and outdoor environments and addresses both near-field and far-field scenarios.

Figure 4-8: Illustration of opportunistic ISAC scenario with RIS.

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

The proposed approach consists of an Artificial Intelligence (AI) architecture to localise users without interfering with communication operations at the RIS. A deep learning model takes the RIS configuration as input and confirms the presence of position information, then another ML model computes the estimate of the maximum achievable accuracy. The information on the UE position is then forwarded to the network, which exploits it to refine resource allocation and orchestration methods, such as the BS and/or RIS beamforming vector selection, mobility management, load/traffic balancing based on the current cell load, etc. The impact of this contribution to such network-level aspects is foreseen to be included in future deliverables.

Results and Discussion

The system demonstrates robust performance across simulations and implementation stages. In the former case, it was observed an average error of 5.04m in large-scale (100m x 100m) deployment, an enhanced direction estimation in far-field conditions, and an accurate distance estimation in near-field scenarios. In the latter, 0.70m average localisation error in indoor environments was achieved with extremely efficient power consumption at 179μJ per position inference. The knowledge of positions obtained with high precision will be handed from the RIS controller to the orchestration to tune its decisions accordingly.

Relation to other 6G-DISAC Contributions

This contribution relates to the contribution #B-7 of [6GDISAC-D31] (Section 5.1.7). Since the sensing application happens independently and opportunistically, the underlying network protocol is assumed to be defined according to existing standards [RISE-D26].

4.1.5 Contribution #O-5: Detecting the Presence of a Non-Cooperative RIS

Motivation and Challenges

Despite the enormous potential RISs have in improving next generation communications, they also introduce new risks. Recent research has demonstrated that even passive RISs can be used to perform various types of eavesdropping and jamming attacks, with very low power requirements. At the same time, methods for detecting the presence of non-cooperative third party RISs have not been developed.

Detecting non-cooperative RISs is essential for maintaining reliable orchestration in distributed ISAC systems. Even without active transmission, such RISs can distort signal paths, interfere with sensing, and undermine coordination among trusted devices. Without detection, resource allocation decisions may be based on false assumptions about the environment, leading to inefficiency or failure.

Deployment Scenario

Consider an environment where a UE device possessing multiple antennas wishes to establish a communication link with a multi-antenna BS. OFDM transmission is adopted, with multiple scatterers being present between the UE and the BS. These scatterers are typically reflectors whose surfaces may be fully or partially covered by RISs that have not been deployed by the communication system’s users and whose behaviour is unknown. The goal of the BS is to reliably and quickly detect the presence of such elements.

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

A novel test statistic is proposed that combines advanced deep learning with a classic change point detection method. More specifically, a deep support vector data description (dSVDD) model is combined with the scan-B test for change detection. The latent space observations outputted by the dSVDD model are processed by the scan-B test.

Results and Discussion

Considering different noise levels and different numbers of sub-carriers the proposed method outperforms two well-known change detection schemes, Hotelling’s T^2 test, and the scan-B test.

Figure 4-9: Performance of the proposed rogue RIS detection strategy (dSVDD-scan B) and baselines in terms of average delay needed for detection over the number of subcarriers.

In fact, Figure 4-9 indicates that the dSVDD-scan B methodology achieves stable performance over a wide range of subcarrier numbers, offering fast rogue RIS detection. At the same time computing the test statistic in real time requires significantly less Central Processing Unit (CPU) time.

4.2 Trade-offs for Dynamic Management of Computing, Communication, and Sensing Resources

ISAC networks must continuously balance competing demands across sensing, computation, and communication. This balance becomes especially critical when devices operate under strict constraints, such as bandwidth, power, or latency. Dynamic management of these resources is therefore not just a matter of efficiency, but of feasibility: determining whether key tasks like localisation or inference can be performed at all. In such settings, resource allocation is tightly coupled with system objectives: minimising ambiguity in sensing outputs, improving positioning accuracy, or ensuring that computation occurs where and when it matters most. The following contributions, as presented in Table 4-2 alongside the relevant contributions of the next subsections, explore these trade-offs through algorithmic strategies that adapt to both the physical environment and the informational needs of the network.

Table 4-2: Physical and signal properties of contributions of Sections 4.2, 4.3, and 4.4.

	Contr. #O-6	Contr. #O-7	Contr. #O-8	Contr. #O-9
Physical deployment				
BSs, antennas, and functional use	Multiple STx BSs	One multi-antenna BS, as STx and SRx	One multi-antenna BS, as STx	One multi-antenna BS, as STx
Ues, antennas, and functional use	Multiple SRx Ues	Multiple Ues with multi-antenna UE, as communication receivers	One multi-antenna UE, as SRx	One multi-antenna UE, as SRx
Passive/active controllable devices in the environment, and functional use	One/Multiple RISs	None	Multiple reflecting/refractive metasurfaces performing computation	Multiple autonomous multi-antenna BSs or RISs for beam-forming
STs	N/A	static or slow-moving ST	Implicit ST	N/A or implicit ST
Nodes with LsePFs	UEs	N/A	STx, SRx, metasurfaces acting as analog processors	Autonomous BSs
Nodes relying on Central SePF	BSs	N/A	N/A	STx, SRx
Types of data in the SeMF	Processed representations	N/A	Abstract sensing signals (e.g. low resolution optical images)	Communication data
Wireless requirements				
Type of radio measurements	CSI	ToA	CSI	CSI
Frequency/bandwidth	Agnostic	Agnostic – narrowband	Agnostic – narrowband	Agnostic – narrowband
Synchronisation requirements	BS-UE-RIS		Among STx, SRx, and metasurfaces	Among autonomous BSs
LoS/NloS conditions	LoS (RIS-UE)	LoS with slow-fading channel conditions	LoS-dominant Ricean	LoS-dominant Ricean

Wireless constraints	Limited communication resources	Limited bandwidth and power budget	Limited power budget	Limited control channel capacity
-----------------------------	---------------------------------	------------------------------------	----------------------	----------------------------------

4.2.1 Contribution #O-6: Resource Allocation for Distributed Positioning

Motivations and Challenges

In cooperative localisation systems, particularly those enhanced with RISs, resource allocation plays a pivotal role in achieving high-accuracy positioning. The motivation lies in the ability to leverage the geometric relationships between transmitters and UEs to optimise positioning performance. By effectively allocating power and selecting transmitters, the system can maximise the sensing performance with available resources. However, several challenges arise in implementing resource allocation for distributed positioning. First, the presence of RISs introduces additional complexity, as their geometric status and configuration affect the localisation accuracy. Second, dynamic network conditions, such as mobility, environment change, and interference, require real-time optimisation of resources. Finally, the heterogeneous nature of devices in the network, including base stations, UEs, and RIS, demands a flexible yet scalable algorithmic approach.

Figure 4-10: Distributed positioning scenario where resource allocation is applied to BS and RIS selection as well as transmission power toward simultaneous localisation of multiple UEs.

Deployment Scenario

The proposed orchestration algorithm is designed for a distributed localisation system involving multiple BSs, multiple UEs, and one or more RISs. In this setup, as shown in Figure 4-10, the BS transmits downlink signals, while UEs actively participate in uplink or sidelink communications to facilitate self-positioning and cooperative positioning. Power allocation at the base station is optimised to ensure efficient signal transmission tailored for precise localisation tasks. In uplink and cooperative localisation, UEs' power allocation is dynamically managed to maximise

the cooperation between devices, which is particularly beneficial in scenarios with limited coverage or severe signal degradation. Furthermore, power allocation of active RISs could also be considered to ensure robust and accurate performance.

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

The orchestration algorithm employs an adaptive and dynamic strategy to optimise resource allocation in distributed positioning systems enhanced by RIS. The algorithm focuses on transmitter selection and power allocation across the base station, UEs, and RIS. By utilising geometric relationships and real-time feedback from the network, it ensures that resources are allocated to maximise localisation accuracy while maintaining efficient energy usage. To handle the dynamic nature of network conditions, machine learning-based methods are integrated into the framework to predict key parameters such as Channel State Information (CSI) and UE mobility patterns. This predictive capability enables proactive resource allocation, ensuring the system is prepared for changes in the environment.

Results and Discussion

This work is still at an early stage. In the update of this deliverable, D4.2, this methodology will be extended and implemented via the incorporation of localisation algorithms from WP3 as well as relevant allocation procedures from WP4, to provide a comprehensive evaluation of RIS-enabled positioning.

4.2.2 Contribution #O-7: Resource Allocation for Trade-off Ambiguity-Accuracy

Motivation and Challenges

Resource allocation in ISAC systems is a complex challenge that requires balancing communication and sensing performance. Achieving this balance involves trade-offs, as optimising one often comes at the expense of the other [LCM+22]. For instance, maximising communication throughput can reduce sensing resolution, while prioritising sensing resolution may degrade communication efficiency. Effective power allocation strategies must address these conflicts to ensure both capabilities function optimally without compromising overall performance.

In OFDM-based ISAC, ToA estimation plays a crucial role in localisation accuracy. However, prioritising communication capacity can introduce ambiguity (strong sidelobes) or reduce estimation resolution [WS22]. A key challenge is maintaining the Peak Side-lobe Level (PSL) constraint [KTA+20], which is essential for avoiding false detections and ensuring reliable Time of Arrival (ToA) estimation. Current approaches typically optimise either PSL suppression or sensing accuracy (e.g., minimising the Cramér–Rao Bound (CRB)) but rarely consider both simultaneously. Furthermore, imposing strict sensing constraints can severely impact communication capacity.

To address these challenges, this contribution introduces a dynamic power allocation strategy that adjusts power distribution across OFDM subcarriers. By jointly optimising ambiguity, accuracy, and communication capacity, this approach ensures a balanced trade-off, preventing unnecessary degradation in any single parameter.

Deployment Scenario

The proposed approach (Figure 4-11) applies to an ISAC network where a BS transmits OFDM waveforms for both communication and sensing. The BS manages power allocation to balance communication capacity and sensing constraints, ensuring reliable ToA estimation and maintaining PSL within acceptable levels in addition to acceptable data rates. UEs receive communication signals, while radar targets represent objects whose locations must be estimated. The system operates under slow-fading channel conditions, and the BS performs the dynamic power allocation strategy to optimise the performance of sensing and communication across varying environments.

Figure 4-11: Deployment of a distributed ISAC system exploiting communication functionality and sensing ambiguity.

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

The proposed dynamic power allocation strategy follows a two-stage optimisation approach. First, the baseline allocation is determined using the Water-Filling (WF) algorithm, which maximises channel capacity without considering sensing constraints. This serves as a benchmark to assess capacity degradation when sensing constraints are introduced. The second stage involves dynamic ISAC power adjustment. Initially, the current PSL and CRB are evaluated based on the WF allocation. If both constraints are satisfied, no modification is required. However, if the PSL constraint is violated, power is redistributed using a PSL-optimal strategy to reduce sidelobe levels. Similarly, if the CRB constraint is not met, subcarrier power is adjusted at the bandwidth edges to enhance ToA estimation accuracy. If these adjustments lead to excessive capacity degradation, the system dynamically switches between communication-only and ISAC modes to maintain an optimal balance. The final power allocation is determined using a binary search strategy, iteratively adjusting between WF, PSL-optimal, and CRB-optimal allocations until an optimal trade-off is achieved.

Results and Discussion

The simulations show the importance of considering both resolution and ambiguity (i.e., PSL) when balancing the trade-off between communication and sensing performance. As shown in Figure 4-12 a loose PSL constraints preserve both accuracy and capacity. However, stricter PSL constraints degrade performance, causing up to 12 Mbits loss in capacity and around 35% drop in accuracy. This trade-off underscores the need for a balanced strategy between sensing and communication. The proposed approach addresses the balance between communication and sensing by using a binary search to dynamically adjust power allocation (for Main Lobe Width (MLW) and PSL). Figure 4-13 shows how the weighting factor impacts capacity, PSL suppression, and accuracy. Prioritising accuracy (Figure 4-13a) improves MLW but reduces suppression and capacity. Conversely, focusing on PSL (Figure 4-13b) worsens MLW and accuracy. These results highlight the trade-offs involved and the value of the proposed dynamic strategy in balancing performance.

It can be inferred that, depending on the constraints and requirements, certain scenarios may not be able to meet all the desired objectives, rendering no feasible power allocation solution. This reinforces the value of the proposed dynamic power allocation strategy, which adapts to meet both sensing and communication needs and switches to a communication-only mode when the desired solution is unattainable.

Figure 4-12: Trade-offs between capacity and accuracy in OFDM ISAC Systems under different PSL constraints.

Figure 4-13: (a) Accuracy Optimisation (b) PSL Optimisation

Related Dissemination

The proposed methodology has been published in conference proceedings, while a relevant patent application has been filed:

Al Khansa, A., Madhusudan, G., Larue, G., & Dufréne, L. A. (2024, November). Dynamic Power Allocation in OFDM ISAC for Time of Arrival Estimation. In 2024 IEEE Conference on Standards for Communications and Networking (CSCN) (pp. 249-254).

Al Khansa, A., Madhusudan, G. Dynamic Resource Allocation for Enhancing Accuracy and Resolution in OFDM ISAC Time of Arrival Estimation”, Application No: FR2410765. Filing date: Oct-2024.

4.3 Contribution #O-8: Distributed Computation on Goal-Oriented Communications

As ISAC systems move towards increased autonomy and context awareness, computation is no longer confined to central nodes but is distributed across the network, closer to where data is sensed and decisions are made. This distributed paradigm enables local processing, reduces response times, and supports real-time adaptation to dynamic conditions. However, embedding

computation at the edge introduces a new set of challenges. These include managing heterogeneous hardware capabilities, variable energy budgets, and thermal or operational constraints, particularly in low-power or embedded platforms.

Goal-Oriented (GO) communication frameworks further shift the focus from transmitting raw data to sharing task-relevant information, often triggering computation only when certain semantic or situational thresholds are met. This coupling between communication and computation demands fine-grained orchestration: deciding not only what to send, but also where, when, and how to compute. In this context, the development of distributed algorithms must account for system-wide trade-offs between computational load, latency, accuracy, and energy efficiency, while ensuring alignment with high-level sensing or control objectives.

Motivation and Challenges

GO communications are expected to play a fundamental role in future 6G and ISAC systems. Apart from the native support of service-level data-transmission applications (e.g., object detection in imagery data), GO approaches find application in the context of data representation, fusion, and distributed processing. The various nodes that participate in the overall procedure are typically associated with diverse requirements especially in terms of power consumption, computation capabilities, and sensing hardware. In parallel, metasurface technologies have been recently investigated as computational entities. In that context, metasurface layers may be used as hidden DNN layers, so that the overall DNN performs OAC, which has tremendous potential in simplifying the computational power requirements. Additionally, treating the system as an end-to-end DNN, the communication resources may also be reduced, since resources are not optimised to provide for unnecessary data rates.

Deployment Scenario

In this work, a solution is proposed to control the wireless environment towards performing task-oriented computations that aid edge-inference objectives of the UE-BS GO system. Precisely, the control over the wireless medium can be achieved via the use of the technologies of reflecting and/or diffracting metasurfaces, namely RISs and/or Stacked Intelligent Metasurfaces (SIMs). Those metasurfaces induce controllable phase shifts on the impinging waves, and can, therefore, shape the channel response, which in turn affects the exact computations performed onto the transmitted signal. Under this viewpoint, the, now reconfigurable, wireless channel can be regarded as hidden DNN layers that perform arbitrary OAC, as illustrated in Figure 4-14. In fact, the phase shifts of the metasurfaces are treated as learnable parameters, identically to typical neural network weights. To this end, the end-to-end architecture can be trained as a single entity through a pertinent variation of the backpropagation algorithm on training data sets to optimise typical learning tasks under varying channel conditions.

Figure 4-14: Illustration of proposed deployment strategy for goal-oriented computation over-the-air integrating stacked metasurfaces as hidden neural network layers.

Figure 4-15: Block diagram and computation flow for the proposed end-to-end goal-oriented framework where the metasurface-parametrizable channel acts as an intermediate DNN component. Both the cases of reconfigurable and static metasurfaces are included, entailing different procedures during the forward and backward passes. Notation explanation and details are given in [SDA25].

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

Assuming availability of the instantaneous CSI that captures the channel responses among all antenna/metasurface elements, the end-to-end system can be characterized by three distinct neural network modules, as shown in Figure 4-15: (i) The transmitter UE that observes input data, pre-processes them, and transmits a signal over the channel; (ii) the transmission module that models the propagation effects of the wireless signal arriving at the BS receiver and includes the effects of the RIS/SIM, given their phase shift configuration vector; (iii) and the receiver module that collects the received signals, post-processes them, and outputs an estimate of the target value to be computed. The overall architecture can be mathematically defined as the composition of the three modules, where the UE and BS are fully trainable, while the transmission module is partially trainable (i.e., the phase shift of the metasurface elements can be configured, but the channel responses of the individual links are treated as random variables). This model can be trained similarly to a typical DNN assuming a collection of a data set of input data and their associated target values, as well as CSI measurements of the wireless environment. The metric to be minimised is the error (such as MSE or binary cross-entropy) between the DNN outputs and the true target values, averaged over the data set and channel realisations. The overall architecture is general enough to admit RIS and SIM devices, with controllable reconfiguration before each transmission or by fixing their configurations after training, while both channel-aware and channel-agnostic transceivers are considered.

Results and Discussion

Reconfigurable architectures, while offering more refined channel control, come at the cost of increased neural network parameters which may impede convergence during training. The presence of a controller additionally implies a dedicated control channel between the metasurface(s) and a computationally-capable entity that is to be utilised at every channel frame before data transmission. While CSI at the endpoints may offer more effective encoding and decoding, it also comes at the cost of increased DNN sizes, since both modules need to extract information from the channel matrices, which scale with the number of metasurface elements. In fact, the static metasurface variation without CSI knowledge has the lowest computational and systemic requirements, as the entirety of the channel coding computations take place over-the-air via the metasurface layers. In terms of selecting the type of metasurface, SIMs are posed as more

Figure 4-17: Performance of different variations of goal-oriented neural networks with integrated over-the-air metasurfaces as computational layers on a classification setup without CSI knowledge at the CSI.

Figure 4-16: Performance of metasurfaces-integrated neural networks compared to no-metasurface and traditional communications baseline over decreasing transmission power levels as training time evolves.

effective computational machinery, since their compact cascaded deployment offers non-linear multi-layer information processing which closely resembles the motivation behind DNNs. To ascertain the above remarks, a numerical evaluation of different variations of the proposed architecture has been carried out, as detailed in Figure 4-16. In this example, even without CSI knowledge, the architecture with a static SIM (comprising 3 layers of 8x8 elements each) can effectively solve an image classification task. Its reconfigurable version exhibited reduced performance due to slow convergence in the same training period, while both RIS variations (each with 25*25 elements) did not result in successful performance despite containing more than three times the number of SIM elements. Furthermore, Figure 4-17 presents an investigation of the minimum power required for successful inference on the sensing task. The metasurfaces-integrated networks as compared with a baseline without any RIS/SIM, as well as with a traditional communication system that sends the sensing data to the SRx, which performs the computational inference task. It is demonstrated that systems relying on metasurfaces-integrated neural networks have the ability to perform successful inference with much lower power budgets, since they utilise the wireless propagation medium as a means for over-the-air computing.

Related Dissemination and relationship with other 6G-DISAC contributions

The algorithmic approach for this work has been published in detail in the following reference, while being under review from IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications:

K. Stylianopoulos, P. Di Lorenzo, and G. C. Alexandropoulos, "Over-the-air edge inference via metasurfaces-integrated artificial neural networks," arXiv preprint arXiv:2504.00233, 2025.

Additionally, this goal-oriented approach is agnostic of the exact application and nature of data. As a result, it may be implemented as a data communication layer among network devices that

perform distributed sensing, capitalising on protocols of Section 3, as well as sensing approached developed under WP3. Finally, the use of network-positioned metasurfaces for reducing the computation needed by the end devices has a close correspondence to the architectural design and KPI evaluation under WP2. Future work in the context of this project will conduct a detailed evaluation of the architectural benefits of this approach.

4.4 Contribution #O-9: Distributed Autonomous Device Co-Configuration with Caching Capabilities

In dense ISAC deployments, multiple devices often share sensing or communication objectives, making it beneficial for their internal configurations (such as beamforming profiles) to be mutually aware or even jointly optimised. As devices gain reconfiguration and sensing capabilities, the notion of autonomous behaviour must expand to include coordination: not just adapting to the environment individually, but doing so in a way that aligns with neighbouring devices. Achieving this in real time requires mechanisms that reduce redundant computation, reuse prior knowledge, and operate effectively within quantization and latency constraints. Caching viable configurations and enabling fast selection logic emerge as practical solutions in this space. This calls for new algorithmic tools that treat configuration as a distributed, cooperative task, tailored to the computational and operational limits of the devices involved.

Motivation and Challenges

In distributed settings such as D-MIMO implemented via ELAAs, relay-systems, or hybrid RISs with sensing capabilities, ISAC functionalities may be substantially enhanced by joint beamforming policies. To fully take advantage of the potential of multiple Beamformer (BFs) devices for wireless operations, precise real-time configuration of the internal states of their unit elements is necessary. In practice, most algorithmic approaches demand the distributed devices to compute appropriate phase profile configurations and switch its elements' responses within the channel coherence time, which implies very stringent requirements in computational delays. Additionally, to facilitate the manufacturing process and reduce the associated costs, various devices are being designed to admit only quantized phase profiles, of a quantisation of even a single bit for cost-efficiency. Effectively, dynamically selecting configurations reduces to discrete optimisation problems that are typically associated with exponential computational complexities and sub-optimal solutions. Despite the great attention D-MIMO systems have recently attracted, the latter two challenges remain still largely unresolved, especially considering the large number of antenna elements, the dynamic nature of the wireless environments typically considered, as well as the computational requirements of the employed optimisation algorithms.

Deployment Scenario

The system under consideration follows closely the deployment scenario and protocol presented in Section 3.3, to highlight the benefits of the distributed computation and cooperation in DNN training and inference. In particular, since the problem is treated from a distributed perspective, each agent ELAA only requires a smaller DNN controller. As illustrated in Figure 3-13 with the deployment set up for the protocol, the cooperating nodes exchange their neural network parameters to achieve federated training. Notice that this information exchange only needs to take place during training. During actual deployment, where inference is applied, Steps 9 and 10 from Figure 3-14 are skipped, alleviating the extra communication overhead at the operation stage.

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

The focus is put on the online orchestration of Multiple-Input Single-Output (MISO) communication systems considering a more realistic, challenging discrete version than the one studied by prior works. A novel DNN tailored for such systems is proposed, which is efficiently optimised with an NE approach. The contributions are summarized as follows: a novel Multi-Branch Attention Convolutional DNN (MBACNN) architecture is presented for the online joint configuration

Figure 4-18: Architecture of proposed DNN for antenna configuration of ELAA/RIS devices based on local CSI.

of the device’s discrete responses and the Tx precoding vector. The different sub-modules of the proposed NN are designed to capture different types of patterns appearing in the channel matrices and impose correlations in the elements of the selected device configurations. The overall architecture is given in Figure 4-18 and is detailed in [SSA25]. To effectively deal with the considered design problem, which is non-differentiable, a simple NE framework to train the proposed MBACNN architecture is introduced. The MBACNN architecture is extended to distributed-BF MISO communication systems and present an NE-based optimisation approach for the online distributed configuration of the phase profiles of the various BFs.

Results and Discussion

An evaluation example is constructed, consisting of a multi-antenna BS as well as multiple hybrid RISs acting as autonomous BFs with local CSI measurements. The extensive numerical investigations over both stochastic and geometrical channels demonstrate that the proposed MBACNN architecture is superior to existing reinforcement learning schemes, lightweight discrete optimisation benchmarks, as well as simple-evolved FFNs with vastly larger numbers of

Figure 4-19: Numerical evaluation of the proposed NE-MBACNN approach for cooperative training of DNN controllers for ELAAs.

trainable parameters, as given in Figure 4-19. In addition, it is showcased that the online distributed optimisation of multiple devices outperforms large, centralised optimisers. It is also interestingly shown that the proposed NE-based training procedure is relatively robust to various changes in its hyper-parameters.

Related Dissemination

The overall network architecture, algorithm, and numerical evaluation have been published in:

G. Stamatelis, K. Stylianopoulos, and G. C. Alexandropoulos, "Evolving multi-branch attention convolutional neural networks for online RIS configuration," *IEEE Transactions on Cognitive Communications and Networking*, to appear, 2025.

Additionally, this orchestration approach makes use of the protocol developed in Section 3.3. Considering the RISs are ELAA devices with individual neural network controllers, the protocol contribution of Section 3.1.3 can be implemented to adhere to the centralized version, used as a benchmark in the numerical evaluation.

5 Conclusion

5.1 Summary of Technical Achievements

This deliverable presents a cohesive framework for enabling distributed ISAC systems, covering protocols, and orchestration strategies tailored for envisioned 6G networks. After a detailed description of the characteristics of DISAC devices, the key opportunities, limitations, and trade-offs were highlighted to provide motivation for the contributions presented in Sections 3 and 4. A range of distinct approaches to communication, sensing, computation, and power has been employed, paving the way for a unified DISAC treatment. In view of the heterogeneity of those devices, support for reconfigurability, caching, and semi-distributed computation have been identified as key objectives of this work, allowing devices to adapt in real time, even under tight resource constraints.

Building on these capabilities, DISAC protocols that manage sensing and communication in heterogeneous and decentralised environments were introduced in Section 3. These include protocol exchange sequences among distributed nodes for detecting connected users and non-connected targets, providing a generic framework for capturing the majority of sensing approaches developed under WP3. Similarly, protocols for distributed control of passive and active devices residing onto the wireless environment, such as RISs, have been developed, in the light of addressing the associated control overheads. Capitalising on diverse system capabilities, protocols for dynamic beam tracking, semantic communication, as well as federated learning

have been additionally proposed to complement the functionalities of the 6G-DISAC architecture.

From the orchestration perspective of Section 4, algorithms were developed for cooperative sensing, localisation, and resource allocation. The sensing and communication objectives were treated as distributed optimisation problems, enabling cooperative, opportunistic, and adversarial algorithms for various detection scenarios. Methodologies were designed to address and exploit the inherent trade-offs, i.e., by balancing ambiguity, accuracy, and energy, offloading computation via OAC, and co-operative learning.

5.2 Cross-WP context and Outlook

The contributions presented in this deliverable comprise the main outputs of the first two tasks for the first 12 months of the lifecycle of WP4. The protocols have been developed largely in parallel to the architectural work of WP2 and are designed to complement the functionality of the components presented in [6GDISAC-D22]. As a result, algorithmic approaches of [6GDISAC-D31] are developed to be aligned with the messaging sequences detailed in Section 3, essentially instantiating variations of those by implementing the functionality in the respective protocol steps. The orchestration methodologies of Section 4 have been developed with the intention of investigating the computational components of the architecture presented in WP2 (LSePF, CSePF, SeMF), in view of the different capabilities of the supported devices. The variety of approaches in terms of scenarios, participating nodes, and system objectives have been largely selected to accommodate the use cases and KPIs of [6GDISAC-D21].

The initial specifications mentioned here constitute a first list of candidate methodologies toward the development of solutions under the proof of concepts of WP5. In that respect, close interaction between the involved WPs is posed to converge to a subset of approaches (in terms of orchestration and resource allocation) that can be analysed further with the intention of experimental demonstration. At the same time, novel methodologies as well as extensions of the ones presented here will be included in the final specifications of D2.4. Finally, the integration of such techniques with the advancements on spectrum management and sharing from Task 4.3 will be investigated in the upcoming period.

6 References

- [3GPP25] 3GPP TS 38.305 v18.5.0, *Stage 2 functional specification of user equipment (UE) positioning in NG-RAN*. Mar. 2025
- [6GDISAC-D21] Deliverable D2.1 "Preliminary version of scenarios, use cases and KPIs", from HORIZON-JU-SNS-2023/6G-DISAC, December 2024.
- [6GDISAC-D22] Deliverable D2.2 "Preliminary version of the distributed ISAC architecture", from HORIZON-JU-SNS-2023/6G-DISAC, December 2024.
- [6GDISAC-D31] Deliverable D3.1 "Initial solutions towards waveforms, sensing, communication, and DISAC", from HORIZON-JU-SNS-2023/6G-DISAC, June 2025.
- [AAS+21] Alamzadeh, I., Alexandropoulos, G.C., Shlezinger, N. *et al.* A reconfigurable intelligent surface with integrated sensing capability. *Sci Rep*, vol. 11, no. 20737, 2021.
- [ADS+22] A. Albanese, F. Devoti, V. Sciancalepore, M. Di Renzo and X. Costa-Pérez, "MARISA: A Self-configuring Metasurfaces Absorption and Reflection Solution Towards 6G," *IEEE INFOCOM 2022 - IEEE Conference on Computer Communications*, London, United Kingdom, pp. 250-259, 2022.

- [AKK+21] Z. Abu-Shaban, K. Keykhosravi, M. F. Keskin, G. C. Alexandropoulos, G. Seco-Granados, and H. Wymeersch, "Near-field localisation with a reconfigurable intelligent surface acting as lens," in *ICC2021-IEEE International Conference on Communications*, pp.1–6, 2021.
- [AML+24] Al Khansa, A., Madhusudan, G., Larue, G., & Dufréne, L. A, "Dynamic Power Allocation in OFDM ISAC for Time of Arrival Estimation," In *2024 IEEE Conference on Standards for Communications and Networking*, pp. 249-254, 2024.
- [AVW22] G. C. Alexandropoulos, I. Vinieratou and H. Wymeersch, "Localisation via Multiple Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces Equipped With Single Receive RF Chains," in *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 1072-1076, May 2022.
- [CAG24] E. Calvanese Strinati, G. C. Alexandropoulos, M. Giyyarpuram, P. Sehier, S. Mekki, V. Sciancalepore, M. Stark, M. Sana, B. Denis, M. Crozzoli, N. Amani, P. Mursia, R. D'Errico, M. Boldi, F. Costanzo, F. Rivet, and H. Wymeersch, "Distributed Intelligent Integrated Sensing and Communications: The 6G-DISAC Approach," *2024 Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications & 6G Summit (EuCNC/6G Summit)*, Antwerp, Belgium, 2024, pp. 392-397.
- [CCS+19] M. Chen, U. Challita, W. Saad, C. Yin and M. Debbah, "Artificial Neural Networks-Based Machine Learning for Wireless Networks: A Tutorial," in *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 3039-3071, 2019.
- [CWH+23] Hao Ran Chi, Chung Kit Wu, Nen-Fu Huang, Kim-Fung Tsang, and Ayman Radwan. A survey of network automation for industrial internet-of-things toward industry 5.0. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 2065–2077, 2023.
- [EDR25] G. Encinas-Lago, F. Devoti, M. Rossanese, V. Sciancalepore, M. Di Renzo, X. Costa-Pérez, "COLoRIS: Localisation-agnostic Smart Surfaces Enabling Opportunistic ISAC in 6G Networks", *arXiv preprint arXiv:2406.07377*, 2025.
- [EZS+20] M. A. Elmoallamy, H. Zhang, L. Song, K. G. Seddik, Z. Han and G. Y. Li, "Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces for Wireless Communications: Principles, Challenges, and Opportunities," in *IEEE Transactions on Cognitive Communications and Networking*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 990-1002, Sept. 2020.
- [GA25] P. Gavrilidis and G. C. Alexandropoulos, "Near-field beam tracking with extremely massive dynamic metasurface antennas," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, under revision, 2025.
- [GMB+25] D. Galappaththige, M. Mohammadi, G. A. Baduge, and C. Tellambura, "Cell-Free Integrated Sensing and Communication: Principles, Advances, and Future Directions," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2502.20345*, 2025.
- [HDC24] N. Hello, P. Di Lorenzo, and E. Calvanese Strinati, "Semantic communication enhanced by knowledge graph representation learning," in *IEEE International Workshop on Signal Processing Advances in Wireless Communications (SPAWC)*, 2024.
- [HFV+23] J. He, A. Fakhreddine, C. Vanwynsberghe, H. Wymeersch and G. C. Alexandropoulos, "3D Localisation With a Single Partially-Connected Receiver

- ing RIS: Positioning Error Analysis and Algorithmic Design," in *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 72, no. 10, pp. 13190-13202, Oct. 2023.
- [HHC+25] N. Hello, M. A. Hamoura, F. Costanzo, F. Rivet, and E. Calvanese Strinati, "Semantic Waveforms for AI-Native 6G Networks," submitted to 25th *International Workshop on Signal Processing and Artificial Intelligence for Wireless Communications (SPAWC 2025)*.
- [KTA+20] Keskin, Musa Furkan, et al. "Peak sidelobe level based waveform optimisation for OFDM joint radar-communications." *17th European Radar Conference (EuRAD)*, 2021.
- [LCM+22] F. Liu, Y. Cui, C. Masouros, J. Xu, T. Xiao Han, Y. C. Eldar, and S. Buzzi, "Integrated sensing and communications: Toward dual-functional wireless networks for 6G and beyond." *IEEE journal on selected areas in communications* vol. 40, no. 6, pp. 1728-1767, 2022.
- [LLL+24] S. Lu, F. Liu, Y. Li, K. Zhang, H. Huang, and J. Zou, "Integrated Sensing and Communications: Recent Advances and Ten Open Challenges," in *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 11, no. 11, pp. 19094-19120, June, 2024.
- [LLM+21] Y. Liu, X. Liu, X. Mu, T. Hou, J. Xu, and M. Di Renzo, "Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces: Principles and Opportunities," in *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, vol. 23, no. 3, pp. 1546-1577, 2021.
- [LSS+23] R. Li et al., "Beam Scanning for Integrated Sensing and Communication in IRS-aided mmWave Systems," in *Proc. IEEE International Workshop on Signal Processing Advances in Wireless Communications 2023 (IEEE SPAWC'23)*, Shanghai, 2023.
- [MBD+14] U. Madhow, D. R. Brown, S. Dasgupta and R. Mudumbai, "Distributed massive MIMO: Algorithms, architectures and concept systems," *2014 Information Theory and Applications Workshop (ITA)*, San Diego, CA, USA, 2014, pp. 1-7.
- [PBD+23] M. Polese, L. Bonati, S. D'Oro, S. Basagni and T. Melodia, "Understanding O-RAN: Architecture, Interfaces, Algorithms, Security, and Research Challenges," in *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 1376-1411, 2023.
- [RISE-D26] RISE-6G, "RISE network architectures and deployment strategies analysis: final results", Deliverable D2.6 https://rise-6g.eu/Documents/LIVRABLES/RISE-6G_WP2_D2.6_FINAL.pdf
- [RYI+24] M. Raeisi, I. Yildirim, M. C. Ilter, M. Gerami and E. Basar, "Plug-In RIS: A Novel Approach to Fully Passive Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces," in *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 23, no. 10, pp. 14776-14789, Oct. 2024.
- [SAI+21] N. Shlezinger, G. C. Alexandropoulos, M. F. Imani, Y. C. Eldar, and D. R. Smith, "Dynamic metasurface antennas for 6G extreme massive MIMO communications," *IEEE Wireless Communications*, vol. 28, no. 2, pp. 106-113, 2021.
- [SCE23] R. P. Sankar, S. P. Chepuri, and Y. C. Eldar. "Beamforming in integrated sensing and communication systems with reconfigurable intelligent surfaces." *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 23, no. 5, pp. 4017-4031, 2023.

- [SDA25] K. Stylianopoulos, P. Di Lorenzo, G. C. Alexandropoulos, "Over-the-air edge inference via metasurfaces-integrated artificial neural networks," arXiv preprint arXiv:2504.00233, 2025.
- [SDD23] M. Sana, H. Dakdouk and B. Denis, "Sensing of Side Lobes Interference for Blockage Prediction in Dense mmWave Networks," *2023 IEEE 34th Annual International Symposium on Personal, Indoor and Mobile Radio Communications (PIMRC)*, Toronto, ON, Canada, 2023, pp. 1-6.
- [SKA24] G. Stamatelis, A. -N. Kanatas, I. Asprogerakas and G. C. Alexandropoulos, "Single- and Multi-Agent Private Active Sensing: A Deep Neuroevolution Approach," *2024 IEEE International Conference on Communications Workshops (ICC Workshops)*, Denver, CO, USA, 2024, pp. 1036-1041.
- [SSA25] G. Stamatelis, K. Stylianopoulos, and G. C. Alexandropoulos, "Evolving multi-branch attention convolutional neural networks for online RIS configuration," *IEEE Transactions on Cognitive Communications and Networking*, to appear, 2025.
- [SSK+18] A. K. Sandu, P. Surarapu, M. A. Khair and R. Mahadasa, "Massive MIMO: Revolutionizing Wireless Communication through Massive Antenna Arrays and Beamforming," *International Journal of Reciprocal Symmetry and Theoretical Physics*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 22-32, 2018.
- [SWD+17] J. Schulman, F. Wolski, P. Dhariwal, A. Radford, and O. Klimov, "Proximal Policy Optimisation Algorithms," *arxiv preprint, arxiv:1707.06347*, 2017.
- [WS22] Wymeersch, Henk, and Gonzalo Seco-Granados. "Radio localisation and sensing—Part II: State-of-the-art and challenges." *IEEE Communications Letters*, vol. 26, no. 12, pp. 2821-2825, 2022.
- [WZD+24] Z. Wang, J. Zhang, H. Du, W. E. I. Sha, B. Ai, D. Niyato, and M. Debbah, "Extremely Large-Scale MIMO: Fundamentals, Challenges, Solutions, and Future Directions," in *IEEE Wireless Communications*, vol. 31, no. 3, pp. 117-124, June 2024.
- [YQZ+22] L. Yan, Z. Qin, R. Zhang, Y. Li, and G. Y. Li, "Resource allocation for text semantic communications," *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, vol. 11, no. 7, pp. 1394–1398, 2022.
- [ZLZ+22] Zhou, Y., Liu, L., Zhao, H., López-Benítez, M., Yu, L. and Yue, Y., "Towards deep radar perception for autonomous driving: Datasets, methods, and challenges". *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 11, pp. 4208, 2022.